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RESISTIRÉ

Reducing gendered inequalities
caused by COVID-19 policies

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Partners

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UDEUSTO
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List of acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
CHW(s)	Community Health Worker(s)
CSO(s)	Civil Society Organisation(s)
EU-27	European Union (27 countries)
FRA	European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights
FS	Factsheet(s)
GBV	Gender-Based Violence
GEP(s)	Gender Equality Plan(s)
ILO	International Labour Organization

LTC	Long-Term Care
NGO(s)	Non-Governmental Organisation(s)
PTSD	Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder
RAS	Rapid Assessment Survey(s)
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
SDC	Statistical Disclosure Control
SRH	Sexual and Reproductive Health
WHO	World Health Organization
WP(s)	Work Package(s)

Summary

The aim of RESISTIRÉ is to understand the unequal impacts of the COVID-19 outbreak and its policy responses on behavioural, social, and economic inequalities in 30 countries (EU-27 plus Iceland, Serbia, Turkey and the UK) and to work towards individual and societal resilience. It does so by mapping policies and social initiatives on the one hand, and collecting quantitative and qualitative data on the other, and by analysing and translating these into insights to be used for designing, devising, and piloting solutions for improved policies and social innovations to be deployed by policymakers, stakeholders, and actors in the field in different policy domains. The project relies on a ten-partner multidisciplinary and multisectoral European consortium, and a well-established network of researchers in 30 countries.

This report gives an overview of the development of the action-ideas that came out of the final cycle of Open Studios³ and how they were further combined with results of the research activities of the third cycle. They have been developed into Operational Recommendations and an Agenda for Future Research.

The Operational Recommendations, designed as RESISTIRÉ factsheets, focus on eight topics: mental health support in times of crisis, access to health services for vulnerable groups, digital transformation for an inclusive post-COVID recovery, promoting sustainable and resilient long-term care, addressing poverty and social exclusion, approaching crisis as a continuum, more representative European data for better intersectional analysis, and transformative funding. The factsheets provide a brief overview of how COVID-19 has made visible or reinforced existing inequalities pertaining to the topic, show personal stories of people affected by them, and give examples of inspiring policies/initiatives to mitigate these inequalities. Finally, the factsheets list several recommendations to various stakeholders that would address these inequalities.

The Agenda for Future Research touches upon six domains, providing a brief analysis of findings from the third cycle of the RESISTIRÉ project, as well as identifying knowledge gaps. It also outlines topics and research questions that future research should address. The six research agendas encompass the topics of health inequalities, inequalities in age and ageing, digitalisation, gender+ inclusive green spaces, civic responses to crisis, and gender-based violence.

³ For more information about the Open Studios, please refer to D5.4.

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Introduction

The aim of RESISTIRÉ is to understand the unequal impacts of the COVID-19 outbreak and its policy responses on behavioural, social, and economic inequalities in 30 countries (EU-27 plus Iceland, UK, Serbia, and Turkey) and to work towards individual and societal resilience. The pandemic has led to the introduction of national policy responses and measures in multiple policy domains to slow infections, prevent deaths, and address some of the socio-economic issues that emerged (Cibin et al., 2021). These measures had profoundly changed lives, with physical and social distancing becoming the new norm and, where needed, quarantining and self-isolation. They had radically shifted how society was organised, with increased working from home, home-schooling, and a general intensification of people's online presence, all with their own specific (un)intended consequences (Axelsson et al., 2021; Bonaccorsi et al., 2020). This new policy framework has also meant furloughing and job losses, with associated economic hardship and mental health issues, and delayed ordinary health treatments (Nicola et al., 2020; Van Bavel, 2020; Lewnard & Lo, 2020). And it has meant increases in the levels of gender-based violence (GBV) and variations in access to support and healthcare.

The impacts of these developments, like those of other crises, are gendered and related to sex, age, disability, ethnicity/race, migration status, religion, social class, and the intersections between these inequalities (Lokot & Avakyan, 2020; Walter & McGregor, 2020; Walby, 2015). The impacts are uneven and unequal, disproportional in their consequences for different groups, and their long-term impacts are uncertain (Cumming et al., 2020). Women have been disproportionately infected by COVID-19 (Sciensano, 2020; Stovell et al., 2021) and affected by its impact; as front-line workers, as formal or informal caregivers in society; as exposed to a higher risk of men's violence, in particular as victims of intimate partner violence. As these positions intersect with social class, ethnicity, age and other inequalities, we deploy a 'gender+' approach, which highlights and builds on gender relations and gender inequalities, but always considering how these intersect with other complex inequalities (Verloo, 2013; Walby et al., 2012). RESISTIRÉ helps to understand how different policy responses are having unequal effects, but also how different responses can be put into place to understand and address gender and intersectional inequalities in different policy domains (Lombardo & Kantola, 2019).

To meet these aims, RESISTIRÉ conducts policy analysis, as well as quantitative and qualitative research activities, to inform the design of innovative solutions. In this way, it responds to the outbreak through co-created and inclusive strategies that address old and new, durable and temporary inequality patterns in and across policy domains. The overall methodology of RESISTIRÉ is based on a step-by-step process running in three cycles over 30 months (April 2021/September 2023). All project activities are organised in these three cycles, feeding results into one another (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 - RESISTIRÉ methodological step-by-step three cycle process

This report provides an overview of the concrete outputs that have been developed in the final cycle of the RESISTIRÉ process for different target groups, namely policymakers, civil society, employers, educational stakeholders, the research community at large - including research funding organisations (RFOs) - and other stakeholders based on the preceding research phase (WP2-4) and the Open Studios (WP5).

The outputs are the results of two activities running in parallel: firstly, the development of Operational Recommendations for policymakers and other stakeholders. Recommendations are presented as factsheets for different types of policymakers (EU, national, regional, local levels) and for different types of stakeholders (civil society organisations (CSOs) & non-governmental organisations (NGOs), employers, etc.). Secondly, there is the systematic monitoring of the analyses of quantitative and qualitative data in each cycle and the development of the Agenda for Future Research to identify knowledge gaps and translate these into research questions. These gaps and questions will be gathered in a [living repository](#) accessible by all partners involved. In previous cycles, a third type of output - the development and launch of Pilot Projects - was pursued as well. Given that the RESISTIRÉ project approached completion at the time of submitting this report, these were not pursued in the final cycle. Nonetheless, some ideas that came out of the Open Studios and had a potential to support the

advocacy activities (T7.4) were selected and further developed. This is the case for⁴:

- Action 2.5: “Platform for knowledge sharing”, which targets organisations involved in the development of community gardens.
- Action 1.4: “Right(s) Now !”, where flash cards are being developed regarding the rights of older people and how these rights were dismissed during the pandemic.
- Action 3.2: “Create conditions for researchers to become activists”, which focuses on creating incentives for researchers to also engage in activism as part of their research and work activities.

These activities will be reported on as part of WP7 reporting.

The first chapter provides more information on the Operational Recommendations. In chapter 2, the Agenda for Future Research is described. The report ends with conclusions.

1. Operational Recommendations

This chapter describes the process that produced and refined the eight factsheets containing operational recommendations and guidelines, followed by each individual factsheet as they were produced in Task 6.1.

Identification of themes for factsheets

The development of the recommendations began after the first (preliminary) insights started to emerge from analyses within WP2, WP3 and WP4. Based on these insights, a Miro board for the development of themes for a set of (initially) six factsheets was shared with the RESISTIRÉ consortium on 16 February 2023 by the task leader (ISAS). The consortium was requested to share any comments and feedback they had, indicate on which factsheets they preferred to work, and share ideas for alternative/additional directions. Consequently, the initial six factsheet topics were complemented with two additional topics (more representative European data and transformative funding) based on further research insights and the results of the final cycle of Open Studios (WP5). In identifying and further refining these recommendations, it was important to ensure that they had an innovative nature, that they could have a real impact, and that there was a balanced approach between different topics and target groups.

First drafts of factsheets

The final eight factsheet topics were presented to the consortium partners, who were again asked to contribute to one or more of them and possibly even take the lead on a

⁴ The initial descriptions of these actions are included and detailed in D5.4.

specific factsheet. Task leaders provided preliminary brief drafts regarding the scope of each factsheet. Then, each factsheet lead developed this further, focusing on writing a problem statement and RESISTIRÉ project research insights, in advance of the subsequent workshop. A factsheet structure was provided - based on the structure used for the second cycle of recommendations - to ensure consistency across the factsheets. Sections included: the recommendations themselves, a problem statement, insights from RESISTIRÉ, and a section dedicated to better stories.

Workshop

To assess and refine the resulting drafts further, a workshop was organised that brought together experts from within and beyond the consortium (see Table 1 below) with specific expertise on the topics covered. One invited expert had to cancel their participation due to unforeseen circumstances shortly before the start of the workshop.

Table 1 - List of Workshop Participants

Invited Participants	Consortium Participants	Consortium Participants (continued)
Marek Havrda	Claudia Aglietti (K&I)	Audrey Harroche (OBU)
Luísa Franco Machado	Ayşe Gül Altınay (SU)	Anne Laure Humbert (OBU)
Gülseren Onanç	Adam Brandstetter-Kunc (ESF)	Aart Kerremans (YW)
Magdalena Pocheć	Marina Cacace (K&I)	Agnieszka Kolasińska (ISAS)
Anna Szczegielniak	Anne-Charlott Callerstig (ORU)	Grace Romeo (YW)
	Vanda Maufras Černohorská (ISAS)	Federica Rossetti (Sciensano)
	Rana Charafeddine (Sciensano)	Lina Sandström (ORU)
	Roberto Cibirin (ISAS)	Sofia Strid (UGOT)
	Sara Clavero (TU Dublin)	Nazlı Türker (SU)
	Alain Denis (YW)	Charikleia Tzanakou (OBU)
	Pınar Ensari (SU)	Nathalie Wuïame (YW)
	Elena Ghidoni (UDEUSTO)	

The workshop was held on 23rd March 2023 in Gothenburg, Sweden, over approximately three hours using posters and sticky notes to adequately capture the participants' feedback. The workshop was divided into two parts, with each part covering four of the eight proposed factsheets. In each part, the experts and consortium participants were divided over four smaller groups and worked concurrently. For each group, a previously designated moderator and note-taker helped facilitate the discussion and

documentation of feedback.

One week before the workshop, the experts had received access to the eight factsheet drafts and, during the workshop and in small groups, they were able to (re)read the recommendations. After everyone had familiarised themselves with the documents, they were asked to provide their initial spontaneous reactions to the recommendations, to reflect on the problem statement, and to think about what the main message of the recommendation should ideally be. Participants were also asked to think of any crucial elements that were missing, what target groups should be addressed and what objectives the recommendations should have. Afterwards, the participants briefly shared their findings with the other groups in order to inform them and elicit any additional comments.

The feedback and input of the experts were taken into account by the leads and supporting contributors when developing the factsheets, altering them where necessary and providing more in-depth recommendations. Several of the initial recommendations were refined and/or altered on the basis of the feedback collected in the workshop. A timeline for the finalisation of the factsheets was also established during the workshop, as well as a structure to follow (based on the structure used for the second cycle of recommendations) to ensure consistency across the factsheets. Sections included: the recommendations themselves, a problem statement, insights from RESISTIRÉ, and a section dedicated to better stories.

Post-workshop

After allowing the factsheet leads and contributors to compile new drafts, a review of the contents of each factsheet was carried out by the task leader ISAS. Subsequently, the documents were edited based on these reviews, and a second round of reviews opened the factsheets up to the comments of the entire consortium. Some of the factsheets were also sent to the external experts who were present in the workshop, to ask for additional comments. Integrating this feedback, the factsheets were finalised and proofread to ensure their readiness for communication and dissemination to the identified target groups. Moreover, the documents were strengthened through the use of visual materials (i.e., infographics), with each factsheet going through a process of identifying the most appropriate messages/content for visualisation and, subsequently, developing and integrating those visuals.

The eight resulting factsheets are included below, with each one centred around a distinct topic/title and target group(s), as indicated in Table 2 below.

Table 2 - Operational Recommendations

Title	Target Group(s)
Mental Health Support in Times of Crisis	Policymakers, employers, education stakeholders, medical practitioners
Access to Health Services for	Public health policymakers, CSOs, activists, equality

Vulnerable Groups	bodies
Digital Transformation for an Inclusive Post-COVID Recovery	Policymakers (members of the European Commission for 'A Europe Fit for the Digital Age'), CSOs
Promoting Sustainable and Resilient Long-Term Care	Policymakers, care service providers, activists
Addressing Poverty and Social Exclusion: A Feminist Perspective	Policymakers, street-level bureaucrats, CSOs
Approaching the Crisis as a Continuum: Learning from an Inclusive Feminist Crisis Response	Policymakers, CSOs, activists
More Intersectional Data	Policymakers, European-level statistics bodies
Transformative Funding: A Pathway for Creative and Effective Crisis Response	Funding organisations

1.1 Mental Health Support in Times of Crisis

Mental health was not a priority in the initial management of the COVID-19 crisis. Attention to this problem arose later, and only after the first serious signs of increased psychological distress among the general population became apparent (e.g. a higher prevalence of depression, anxiety, post-traumatic stress, more widespread suicidal thoughts, increased domestic violence). Now that the crisis appears to be over, its impact on people's psychological wellbeing is still difficult to measure, evaluate, and address, but its side effects persist. Moreover, mental health problems have primarily been considered a consequence of the pandemic, but this neglects pre-existing factors that played a role in mitigating or exacerbating the impact the COVID-19 crisis had on the general population. Systematic data collection would provide insights into which groups have been most at risk of developing mental health problems and why, and, in the event of a future crisis, it would help to predict the differential impacts of policy measures. In addition, data collection would provide a basis for developing a prevention-oriented approach at the European level to facilitate the early detection and timely treatment of mental health issues.

Recommendations

Mental health must be an integral part of any crisis intervention from the very beginning

Health authorities need to recognise the importance of psychological factors when dealing with infectious disease outbreaks. Addressing mental health needs from the very beginning of a crisis plays a key role in the prevention of elevated psychological distress

in the population, which in turn helps to avoid additional social and economic burdens. It is imperative to provide access to mental health services and support to everyone, regardless of their socioeconomic status, national origin, age, etc. To this end, European governments need to revisit their investments in the mental health sector, strengthen community-based health services, and prepare comprehensive, long-term strategies addressing increased demand in mental health support.

People with existing severe mental health problems should be considered a risk group during a health crisis

The COVID-19 pandemic had a significant negative impact on the mental health of people who previously suffered from severe disorders, both because of their pre-existing health conditions but also because they tend to be more socially vulnerable. Moreover, owing to restrictions that did not sufficiently take this group into account, opportunities for early intervention were missed. In preparing for future pandemics, policymakers and healthcare institutions should consider patients with severe mental illness as a priority and plan for their continued access to primary and specialised support and care services.

The implementation of prevention programmes and the early detection of mental health problems starting at school age

COVID-19 and its restrictions had an impact on the wellbeing of young people. Since then, more emphasis has been placed on helping children and adolescents to learn about their own mental health, recognise their emotions, discuss their feelings, and seek help when needed. However, if individual families are left alone to perform the task of mental health support, there is a risk of there being increasing gaps in mental health treatment that result from the fact that families might not have adequate resources to deal with these problems (e.g. financial resources or knowledge). An additional risk is the increased burden of care that parents have to bear, which in turn could have repercussions on their mental and physical health. Educational systems should play a crucial role in the direction of both the prevention and the early detection of mental health problems. For example, integrating projects and activities on mental wellbeing into curricula starting in the early educational stages would have beneficial effects for students in the short and long term and would help them deal with crisis situations. Regarding detection, increased and continuous collaboration between the educational and mental health sectors is necessary in order to identify mental health problems in children. Mental health should be addressed in educational policies at all levels (local, regional, national) and thus promote the Mental Health in All Policies approach (Rampazzo et al., 2016; Botezat et al., 2020).

Alternative support services such as community-based crisis intervention and peer support programmes should be strengthened

Given the unmet need for mental health support by the general population that occurs especially during crisis periods, it is necessary to overcome the problem of long waiting lists and implement affordable services. As suggested by the WHO (2009), the base of its Pyramid for an Optimal Mix of Services for Mental Health – namely, informal community care – should be strengthened, as these services are generally accessible and acceptable because they constitute an integral part of the community. Greater investments are therefore needed in preparatory trainings for potential peer support specialists and volunteers, who could leverage their lived experiences to support others struggling with psychological distress.

Promote the systematic and dynamic collection of mental health data for the general population

An important instrument for monitoring the population's mental health are national health surveys, which make it possible to identify groups that are more at risk of developing mental health issues and to understand the causes of these issues and the factors that lead to these groups being more at risk. The collection of intersectional data should be promoted in these health surveys (see also RESISTIRÉ Factsheet No. 21) in order to identify risk groups. Moreover, the collection of these data should be performed dynamically and frequently to enable the up-to-date monitoring of the population's mental health, while accounting for hard-to-reach groups such as undocumented migrants, homeless people, people living in residential settings, etc. The use of instruments for measuring mental health among the population in general and at-risk groups more specifically, such as the Rapid Assessment Surveys (RAS), should be promoted even beyond the pandemic crisis.

Achieve the right balance between digital and traditional channels of mental health support

Exploiting the opportunities offered by technology in public services and healthcare is important to increase prevention actions and to expand outreach of mental health support. However, to avoid the emergence of new inequalities and the reproduction of existing ones, systems based on traditional settings should be continued and it should not be assumed that digital is a one-size-fits-all solution. Digital services may be more difficult to access by people with limited resources, people without digital skills, or people who are more reluctant to use mental health services that do not occur face-to-face (see also RESISTIRÉ Factsheet No. 17).

Problem Statement

Mental health is characterised by emotional wellbeing, good behavioural adjustment, relative freedom from anxiety and disabling symptoms, and an ability to form constructive relationships and cope with the ordinary demands and stresses of life (VandenBos, 2015). The World Health Organisation recognises that **mental health can**

be affected by socioeconomic crises or by political measures taken to contain the outbreak of disease (WHO Regional Office for Europe, 2022). Most studies on the subject have shown that infectious **disease outbreaks are associated with a higher prevalence of mental health-related symptoms** (e.g. depression, anxiety, insomnia) in survivors and their families, among healthcare workers, and in affected communities (Cénat et al., 2021).

The context of the COVID-19 pandemic, and the **huge sudden disruption in people's routines**, contributed to the detrimental impact on mental health. Social distancing and self-isolation, loneliness, concerns about the health of oneself and one's loved ones, fear of job loss, financial insecurity, the forced change of daily habits and working conditions, all had the effect of **exacerbating fear, anxiety and depression in the general population** (Fiorillo & Gorwood, 2020; Fountoulakis et al., 2022).

The most recent data from the fifth round of the Eurofound e-survey (May 2022) show that mental wellbeing in the EU is currently below the level it was at before the pandemic (Eurofound, 2022). Several other studies have reported evidence of a worsening of mental health in the general population worldwide and an increase in depression and anxiety, which has had an impact on family dynamics and people's daily lives. People with a **history of mental disorders** have been impacted even more severely (Fountoulakis et al., 2022). The COVID-19 pandemic is also known to have had an impact on the **mental health of children and young people**, although this has not yet been systematically analysed (Kauhanen et al., 2022).

At the same time, **mental health services have been severely disrupted** since the outbreak (World Health Organization, 2022). In-person contacts with doctors were drastically limited and replaced by remote modes of support; staff and infrastructure were redistributed; long-term residential facilities were isolated from the outside world. The combination of these two dynamics - an increased need for help in the face of reduced supply - has inevitably led to the gradual surge in **unmet mental health needs**.

While it is expected that much of the adverse effect of the pandemic on mental health will slowly attenuate, negative impacts may persist in the case of vulnerable groups such as young people, **people with pre-existing serious mental illness⁵, and socially excluded people** (Moreno et al., 2020). Regarding people with pre-existing conditions, one of the underlying reasons for this is the limited attention that has been paid to patients with psychiatric disorders in policy responses. Even though they were recognised as groups particularly vulnerable to the direct (increased risk of infection, a

⁵ **Serious mental illness (SMI)** is defined as a mental, behavioural, or emotional disorder resulting in serious functional impairment, which substantially interferes with or limits one or more major life activities. The burden of mental illnesses is particularly concentrated among those who experience disability due to SMI. National Institute of Mental Health, https://www.nimh.nih.gov/health/statistics/mental-illness#part_2542.

severe course of COVID-19) and indirect (loss of income, lack of access to medical care, suicidal behaviour) effects of the pandemic (De Picker et al., 2021; Moreno et al., 2020), only a few countries explicitly addressed mental illness in their policy responses to the pandemic.

This reflects a general tendency to **overlook the effects of crises on mental health and wellbeing**. Instead, greater recognition of the psychological consequences of crises, especially in their most acute phases, is needed. Psychological factors not only determine individual reactions to distress, they also play an important role in the population's adherence to public health measures (e.g. social withdrawal) and in reducing maladaptive and socially disruptive pandemic-related behaviour (e.g. panic buying) (Cullen et al., 2020; Taylor, 2019).

Insights from RESISTIRÉ

Data collection on mental health: opportunities and limitations

The evidence gathered by the quantitative work package in RESISTIRÉ indicates that there is a gap in terms of the systemic and frequent collection of comprehensive data on health including mental health. Detailed and large-scale intersectional analysis was found to be largely non-existent, apart from the analysis of some basic sociodemographic factors and gender differences (see also RESISTIRÉ Factsheet No. 21).

RAS carried out during the COVID-19 pandemic contributed greatly to providing dynamic snapshots of population mental health during the crisis, both because of the **high frequency** with which they were conducted and for their ability to reach **specific target groups** (such as immigrants, LGBTQI+ communities, older people) that are generally more difficult to reach with general population surveys.

The results of the RAS collected within RESISTIRÉ suggested that COVID-19 had a greater impact on the mental health of specific target groups than it did on the general population (Harroche et al., 2023). For example, an analysis of data from a Eurofound e-survey (Eurofound, 2020) revealed that those who identified as 'other' in the survey's question on gender were more likely to score lower on the mental wellbeing scale than those who identified as female or male. Although the number of people who selected this gender response was low in each round of the survey, these findings constitute an important starting point in support of the idea that more **refined data should be collected using an intersectional lens to monitor the mental health status of people in different groups**. Thanks to the characteristics of these surveys, RAS could serve this function and could be integrated as permanent tools in national mental health monitoring and prevention programmes.

People with severe mental health problems did not receive sufficient

attention during the crisis

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the focus on combating the virus meant that other areas of health care, including mental care, were side-lined. Most human and economic resources were allocated to COVID-19 and intensive care units. For **people with severe mental health problems** (Zimmerman, Morgan & Stanton, 2018), this meant becoming even more invisible. From the outset, in many countries, there was no consideration of whether people with mental disorders were **able to comply with the restrictions and rules** established during the pandemic and what effect this would have on **their psychological condition** and on that of **their caregivers**. People with serious mental illness experienced feelings of despair, fatigue, and aggravation during the pandemic, when mental health facilities were closed, as reported in a RESISTIRÉ narrative:

'I am a woman, the mother of a boy with a severe mental disorder. [...] His disability has worsened since the outbreak of the pandemic, and his unreasonable behaviours have multiplied. He has also fallen into depression; I can tell because when I get home from work, at 7 pm, he is already asleep. The day-care centre has recently reopened, but only for three mornings a week. I often go to the office with a sense of guilt, knowing that I am leaving my son at home, all day, without any stimulus or professional help.' (60-year-old woman from Italy)

Only a limited number of European countries – the United Kingdom, Germany, the Netherlands, Denmark, the Czech Republic, and Latvia – included people with severe mental disorders among vulnerable groups for special consideration from the very beginning of the health crisis – for example by giving them priority in the distribution of available vaccines. In other countries, specific attention to them was not prioritised.

School closures exposed children and adolescents to emotional distress

The global health crisis and related policy measures to contain the spread of the virus had an exacerbating effect on mental health problems such as depression and anxiety among young people. Among the risk factors, confinement and social isolation **experienced during school closures were particularly relevant for the youngsters**. RESISTIRÉ analysis showed that the shift to online education meant that many students were confined to their parents' homes, which sometimes resulted in experiences of **regression and the loss of privacy and independence**.

The family and family dynamics were often significant sources of psychological problems because of the excessive and forced closeness of family members during the pandemic, which many families were not at all accustomed to, as depicted in the following narrative:

'We were quarantined in our own flat by our dad, who took control on the grounds of an emergency, even though we had been

independent for years, but now he was controlling who we could see and how. This caused so much tension that my sister and I moved to another flat for a week, and then we moved back home with new living arrangements. But after that our family life became very peaceful [...] In hindsight, it was difficult to move back home to my parents because of COVID, because the calm environment, my parents' care, the fact that my dad even read my exam essays, made me forget what I was capable of (23-year-old woman from Hungary).

The problem of having to spend time in confinement with one's family was particularly difficult for LGBTQI+ people, whose parents were not always understanding or supportive. In addition, students, parents, and educators alike often reported that schools and governments offered little support and showed little understanding of the **negative effects of online education in terms of mental health.**

Although the importance of educational facilities for the social and emotional lives of students has come to be strongly recognised, schools do not always have the resources or knowledge to support students from an emotional perspective, to pay attention to their psychological wellbeing, to discuss their feelings, and to encourage them to ask for help when needed. **Educational programmes** are often underfunded and **too overburdened by curricular requirements to address the issue of personal wellbeing.** Moreover, although teachers can be key facilitators, they cannot be expected to take on this role as well. Therefore, the mental health of young people, and how schools can contribute to it, remains both a challenge and a goal that needs to be pursued in the current times of recurring crises.

The psychological impact of policy measures that view the household as a self-sufficient system

The analysis made in by RESISTIRÉ showed that many families in the general population experienced the pandemic as a traumatic event. The unpredictability and relentlessness of the pandemic, combined with the added effect of persistent financial, work, and care obligations, meant that **parents were unable to maintain effective coping mechanisms** in the face of excessive pressures (Stovell et al., 2022).

They had to support additional needs crucial to the wellbeing of their children that were usually met by the school, peers, or other relatives (study activities and the need to play). Interactions between grandchildren and grandparents were severely limited as older people were considered an at-risk group, and this **decreased the practical support that parents would usually receive** from grandparents (Sandström et al., 2022). In turn, the **mental health of older adults who were previously involved in caring activities** was also negatively impacted by their being unable to care for their grandchildren (Stovell et al., 2022). Teleworking often had the effect of blurring the boundaries between work and the private lives of parents, which negatively affected the mental

health of some. Women, who had to combine paid work with increased unpaid care work, in particular found this situation difficult to cope with. Moreover, the increased demands of caring for others usually meant that the people doing so had to deprioritise their own wellbeing, as reported in one RESISTIRÉ narrative (see also RESISTIRÉ Factsheet No. 5):

I live with my two children aged 11 and 15 in a village. The Corona pandemic suddenly left me and my two children at home. I often had online meetings, and during breaks I tried to help the kids and coordinate the assistants' work. However, I feel I failed in all of this.

My mother played an important role in raising my children. Before the pandemic, she travelled from Belgium every Thursday to take care of them. During the pandemic, this was no longer possible. My children did not see her for six months, which was like losing a parent for them. The multitude of painful situations like this caused me to burn out. For the past year, I have been exhausted and I've developed heart problems. When I am overstressed, my heart palpitates, and there are disturbances to its rhythm. I still have a long way to go to recover. (43-year-old woman from the Netherlands).

Unequal access to (digital) healthcare services

During the COVID-19 crisis, there were significant disruptions in the delivery of mental health services, which rapidly shifted to new modes of delivery – most notably, the **use of digital mental health care** (OECD, 2021). In the NRRPs that RESISTIRÉ mapped, digital inclusion is often seen as a universal good that will benefit all, including vulnerable groups. In contrast, the negative effects of **digitisation, including its potentially negative impact on gender and intersectional equality, receive much less attention**. Digital inequality is often intertwined with other inequalities in society related to age, disability, migration, socioeconomic background, and geographical location, as they constrain digital access, in terms of both the availability of tools and literacy. Other negative effects highlighted by RESISTIRÉ data are the spread of misinformation online and the **loss of valuable aspects of service delivery** when these services are moved online, and this is especially true in the case of healthcare and mental healthcare.

Although some digital inequalities can be mitigated by ensuring that everyone has access to digital tools and the competence to use them, what these negative impacts demonstrate is that the 'solution' may not always be digital. **Access to existing mental health services should be provided either in-person or via telemedicine.**

Better Stories

- **Care Fair project - Promoting mental wellbeing through schools (Czech Republic).** One of the pilot projects implemented under RESISTIRÉ is by the organisation Nevypust' Duši and it is a thematic event held at a high school in the Czech Republic and organised like a fair, with stands, workshops, lectures, and other activities designed to share information about wellbeing and access to psychological help. The project is meant to address the real mental health needs among students in that school, as the topics covered in the fair are chosen by the students themselves, who are active co-creators of the event. Putting them in touch with organisations/NGOs/experts active in the field of wellness is expected to reduce the barriers to seeking help faced by students.
- **In Iceland, social gatherings in a local café were organised every week in an effort to reduce isolation.** With the aim of supporting families, older people, and disadvantaged people, a local CSO applied for and received a grant from its municipality to set up a cafeteria. The cafeteria was run for eight weeks in the summer of 2020. People could come in and enjoy the company of other people for coffee and a snack without having to pay. The aim of the project was to encourage social ties in the aftermath of the isolation imposed on them in the previous months to contain the spread of COVID-19.
- In **Germany**, a **government programme** was launched in 2020 **to support women's counselling centres**, as they were deemed suitable to provide a direct and effective response in the context of the pandemic crisis. Until that year, very few women's counselling centres were equipped with sufficient technical and communication tools; many centres lacked computers, mobile phones, and Wi-Fi. The staff also lacked digital know-how. The programme managed and allocated millions in federal funding to women's counselling centres that applied for a grant. In total, 2.7 million euros were forwarded to some 700 institutions, thanks to which 800 projects for the expansion of digital services were implemented. The total project duration was two years.
- An association in **Serbia** managed the **continuation of care service for persons with intellectual disabilities during the lockdown**. Because of the state of emergency, the users could not leave their houses and had no more direct contact with their mentors. Therefore, the Serbian organisation's team reorganised support for persons with intellectual disabilities living in independent accommodation and provided additional activities to preserve their psychological and physical wellbeing. The team organised various workshops (fitness, music, and creative workshops). These took place via Internet applications for group chat. In addition to the existing services for patients, the organisation also provided **additional activities and support for the members of a patient's family**.

1.2 Access to Health Services for Vulnerable Groups

The COVID-19 pandemic caused huge backlogs and delays in healthcare, further worsening the situation of already vulnerable groups (e.g. migrants, ethnic minorities, people with disabilities, homeless people). The interruption of services

that were not considered essential (e.g. sexual and reproductive healthcare, rehabilitation, addiction treatment) took a tremendous toll on marginalised groups and communities. The lack of data on the health and wellbeing of people living outside the healthcare system is likely to result in a gross underestimation of the scale of the problem of unmet medical needs during and following the pandemic. In order to address systemic inequalities in healthcare, it is imperative to identify and recognise the categories of patients whose medical needs are most likely to be put on hold in times of crisis.

Recommendations

Reconceptualising health: a holistic approach

Healthcare, even in the heat of a crisis, should always do more than just provide sporadic care and respond to acute health problems. In order to effectively tackle the challenges that public health emergencies create and mitigate the long-term risks they pose to societies, and to meet the challenges of an ageing society, a holistic and functional approach to health is required. Care should become more preventive and patient-centred and the policy focus should expand and go from 'putting out fires' to embracing a more comprehensive strategy that addresses the full complexity of physical, psychological, and social needs of patients. Healthcare services should be aimed not only at reversing illness but also at restoring health and ensuring continuity of care. Therefore, policy objectives should include providing access to physical and psychosocial rehabilitation, mental health support, and interventions to restore fitness for work, etc.

The systematic collection of data and mapping of vulnerable populations in healthcare

In order to identify the populations who are most likely to experience particularly serious negative health outcomes of emergencies, it is necessary to systematically collect data on population characteristics and vulnerabilities. Identifying at-risk populations is essential for determining potential resource needs and actions that should be taken by policymakers and public health professionals to the mitigate direct and indirect effects of public health emergencies on population health. It is essential to collect data on health-risk factors on a regular basis, as the dimensions of health inequalities may vary depending on the stage and nature of the crisis. To this end, governing bodies, CSOs, healthcare practitioners, epidemiologists, and other relevant stakeholders need to be in constant dialogue.

Healthcare systems need to leverage community healthcare

For healthcare systems to be resilient against health emergencies of the magnitude of the COVID-19 pandemic, there needs to be a reorganisation of the delivery of primary

health services. Community health workers (CHWs) can help to maintain continuity of care for people with chronic conditions and can provide urgent and emergency health services directly in the areas in which vulnerable communities live. Delegating some health services and responsibilities to community healthcare not only alleviates the pressure on the healthcare system in times of crisis, it also helps to advance health equity and to respond to local medical needs.

Sustainable financing of CSOs working with vulnerable groups

For the healthcare system to respond more accurately to the needs of the most vulnerable, patients' voices need to be heard. One way for marginalised groups to express their needs is through the civil society organisations that support and represent them. Not only are CSOs able to provide timely emergency assistance in times of crisis, they also have well-established, long-lasting, trusting relationships with vulnerable communities. To ensure that civil society can continue to help those in need, especially in the midst of a crisis, the current funding scheme needs to move from a short-sighted, project-based approach to more sustainable, long-term solutions.

Creating better working conditions for healthcare workers

Achieving health equity will only be possible once the problem of the poverty-level wages and high-risk working conditions some healthcare workers face is addressed. The most undervalued and underpaid employees within the healthcare system on the whole are disproportionately women and immigrants. At the same time, they are the ones who make up the vast majority of frontline workers, who faced particular occupational challenges during the COVID-19 pandemic. Elevated psychological stress, long shifts, heavy workloads, and the risk of work-related infections led many healthcare workers to leave their professions, which in turned further exacerbated the conditions of those who stayed. Setting equitable wages in the healthcare sector is the first step towards improving the lives of essential workers. Introducing Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) in the healthcare sector as a standard practice is also of critical importance. As a proven method for systematically promoting gender equality and diversity, GEPs help to dismantle discriminatory labour practices.

Universal access to good-quality and non-discriminatory sexual and reproductive health services

Despite women's right to sexual and reproductive health (SRH) being recognised as an essential part of their right to health, discriminatory financial barriers, entrenched social norms, and gender stereotypes continue to impede access to quality SRH services for a significant part of the population. In order to guarantee the availability, accessibility, and quality of SRH care, states must ensure that this area of healthcare receives sufficient budgetary allocations. It is vital to eliminate all forms of discrimination against women in fulfilling their right to SRH. This means including a full range of SRH services in universal

health coverage and eliminating policies that criminalise or obstruct women's access to services such as abortion or modern contraception.

Problem Statement

As the WHO Constitution (World Health Organization, 1946) states, *'the highest attainable standard of health [is] a fundamental right of every human being'*. In other words, **access to health** services should be a **universal human right**, rather than a privilege. Despite the right of access to healthcare and medical treatment being one of the central topics on the agenda of the EU (De Vito et al., 2016), research shows that **health inequalities are persistent and tend to affect the most vulnerable groups** (Orzechowski et al., 2020).

Access to healthcare is highly dependent on the amount of investment in health systems (Forster, Kentikelenis & Bambra, 2018) and it has been shown that **public expenditures on healthcare tend to severely decrease in the aftermath of an economic crisis** (Spasova, Vanhercke & Coster, 2018; Carney & Ostrach, 2020). Many European healthcare systems have suffered years of **underfunding and underinvestment** in the medical workforce, which left them deeply unprepared for the COVID-19 pandemic (Iacobucci, 2021). From the **shortage of hospital beds and medical equipment to the shortfall of health professionals**, COVID-19 has laid bare the consequences of decreased spending in the sector of public health (Jensen, Kelly & Avendano, 2021). Reduced investments in some cases also contributed to the increased privatisation of healthcare providers (Maarse, 2006; Buzelli & Boyce, 2021), creating an additional divide between those who can afford better, more expensive care in private institutions and those who cannot.

Because of the **hospital capacity strain** caused by the public health emergency, people in need of **non-urgent medical care**, such as those living with chronic conditions, were less likely to have their needs met during the pandemic (OECD, 2021). As the majority of human and economic resources of healthcare systems were invested into fighting the virus and preventing it from spreading, many patients living with chronic conditions or requiring ambulatory care experienced disruptions to or the suspension of medical services. Recent Eurofound (2021) results recorded a **significant rise in unmet needs across all European Union countries both in summer 2020 and spring 2021**. Based on the Eurofound sample from June-July 2020, a **much higher percentage of women than men reported a rise in unmet medical needs** since the start of the pandemic in the EU. In addition, the health and wellbeing of those overlooked by the healthcare system, who are the **most vulnerable groups** in terms of the right to access healthcare (i.e. migrants or homeless people), remain largely unobserved due to data scarcity. In order to address the physical, mental, and social health needs of vulnerable people, a comprehensive strategy allowing for the identification of those who are most likely to be overlooked by the system in times of crisis is needed and patients' voices must be heard.

Moreover, for healthcare systems to be resilient against health emergencies and to be able to maintain continuity of care for people with chronic conditions, strong primary and community healthcare is essential (OECD, 2021). Healthcare services need to be extended and brought closer to vulnerable communities and should go beyond acute care. A shift in the perception of what constitutes healthcare is needed so as to recognise that the role of health services is not only to reverse illness but also to restore health.

Insights from RESISTIRÉ

The consequences of decreased spending on the public health sector

Access to healthcare tends to decrease during periods of economic recession. In Italy, for example, austerity policies enacted following the 2008 economic crisis led to a severe decrease in funding, which ultimately created a healthcare system that was less prepared to respond to the pandemic (Buzelli & Boyce, 2021). Regrettably, this issue is not specific to Italy. An analysis of RESISTIRÉ narratives clearly reveals the impact of the **shortage of healthcare workers and how this increased the workload and emotional burden** experienced by medical staff during the pandemic. The unprecedented need to increase capacity in intensive and acute care wards resulted in medical personnel from other care pathways - often with little or no experience, training, or preparation - being deployed in intensive care wards (Stovell et al., 2022), as described by one nurse who was interviewed:

'There is a consistent shortage of staff in the hospital, especially when it comes to nurses. To counteract this, nurses were moved between different wards. This produced chaos and stress. For example, staff were transferred to areas outside of their expertise. They did not know their new colleagues, the patients, or the processes in place. This is extremely bad for day-to-day work as this type of knowledge is essential for being able to act quickly [...] We did 13-hour shifts, including an unpaid lunch break. However, often there was no time for a break.' (24-year-old nurse from Austria).

RESISTIRÉ highlights how **healthcare workers had to shoulder some of the heaviest burdens caused by the pandemic and how there is a clearly observable gender divide in this**, as the majority of high-risk healthcare positions are occupied by women. RAS analysed within the framework of the project show that there has been a consequent **deterioration in the mental health of frontline workers**. The pressure they experienced during the state of emergency led many of them to leave their professions, which inevitably made the conditions of those who stayed even worse. The psychological difficulties that essential workers faced during the pandemic are illustrated by the following testimony from a 46-year-old nurse living in Sweden:

'I probably have PTSD⁶, just like my colleagues. I dare not show that I am one of them, as I'm the one caring for many patients with PTSD. I should get help. You're not wiser than you are. In addition to therapy, we have a counsellor and a hospital chaplain. We haven't used that either. Most nurses come to work and throw themselves into whatever tasks they're given, and you just don't focus on yourself, even if it is more than eight hours.'

The persistently excessive workload experienced by workers in the healthcare sector, coupled with personnel shortages, also had negative effects on people in need of medical assistance. Many of the RESISTIRÉ expert interviewees referred to an accumulated **health debt** resulting from **postponed treatments, delayed medical screenings (i.e. mammograms), and preventive health measures**. This was reflected in multiple narratives collected from vulnerable groups:

'I had to postpone most of them [preventive examinations] because hospitals were not offering these services. This was at the beginning [of the pandemic] and now as well [January 2022] because there are many COVID cases and deaths. My doctors advised me to go to private centres to get the examinations for my health, otherwise I would have to wait for a month. I am a bit worried that I might fall ill because of my age, and I won't find out early enough to get treatment.' (74-year-old woman living in Greece)

These changes in health practices and behaviours are predicted to have multidimensional negative effects. Not only are they likely to have a long-term impact on population health outcomes, they also impose an added strain on medical staff following the re-opening of non-acute healthcare services.

The suspension of sexual and reproductive health services

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the attention given to fighting the virus meant that **other areas of healthcare were deprioritised**, as most human and economic resources were directed towards COVID and intensive care wards. **Sexual and reproductive health services** stand out in this regard and have taken a toll on women's health. In Romania, for instance, during the state of emergency all medical services and surgical interventions considered non-essential were suspended. This created a grey area in relation to abortion-on-demand, with only **11% of Romanian hospitals** performing this procedure during the state of emergency. In the Czech Republic, the distribution of contraceptive methods in primary care clinics was disrupted, which resulted in increased cases of unwanted pregnancies.

⁶ **PTSD** – post-traumatic stress disorder.

In addition, the deprioritisation of sexual health had a negative impact on **transgender people**, as services such as gender reassignment surgery were deemed elective and therefore postponed. In France, services like hormone therapy, fertility preservation, and gender-affirming surgery for transgender individuals were suspended during the emergency. The increasing lack of attention to the healthcare needs of transgender people is exemplified by the following testimony:

'As a transwoman I've often experienced a lack of service, especially regarding healthcare. This has gotten worse during COVID, as all waiting lists have gotten longer, and it is hard to get answers. It's really hard and hurtful to feel like a residual. A lack of funding is the reason for the few and poor services. For example, I was supposed to have my gender reassignment surgery a year ago, but it was postponed because of COVID.' (50-year-old transwoman from Iceland)

RESISTIRÉ's analysis using Eurofound data indicates that accessing healthcare was a particular issue for LGBTQI+ communities. The findings show that people who do not identify as female or male had greater unmet medical needs (Figure 1). Unmet medical needs were reported more often by people who identified 'in another way' than by people who identified as female or male (approximately 40% vs 20%)⁷. Importantly, **this inequality appears to have widened as the pandemic progressed**. As Figure 1 shows, the proportion of those who reported an unmet need between the summer of 2020 and the spring of 2021 increased by 10 percentage points for this group.

⁷ The sample size of people who identified 'in another way' was rather small, ranging from 100 people (0.4% of the sample) in summer 2020 to 391 people in spring 2021 (0.8%). While estimators calculated from the sample data may be imprecise, it is still important to report them in the context of the LGBTQI+ data gap.

Figure 1: Percentage of the population with unmet medical needs (wave 1 and wave 2)
Source: Authors' computation, Eurofound 'Living, Working and COVID-19' survey

The most vulnerable patients are those most likely to be forgotten

During the pandemic **existing health-related inequalities were exacerbated** and it became almost impossible for vulnerable groups to access primary health care services. Deficiencies in the social security and national health insurance systems in many countries have resulted in **major health consequences for groups who were already suffering from the effects of structural inequalities** (Axelsson et al., 2021). As RESISTIRÉ's research findings revealed, multiple inequality groups have been affected by limited access to quality health services during the crisis. Women and girls, especially in **rural and marginalised communities**, struggled to receive adequate treatment and medical care. This was compounded by multiple and intersecting inequalities, such as **ethnicity, socioeconomic status, disability, age, race, geographic location, and sexual orientation**.

Discrimination on the grounds of race or nationality has been observed in many countries. There is evidence of a **higher morbidity and mortality rate from COVID-19 among ethnic minorities**. The scoping literature review and RESISTIRÉ RAS analysis revealed that migrant populations also had difficulty accessing healthcare during the crisis. Difficulties in accessing medical services meant that **non-native populations were less likely to undergo COVID-19 screenings and treatment**, which in turn may

have increased their infection and mortality rates (Stovell et al., 2022). Along with **people in precarious or informal employment and people in a situation of homelessness**, migrants were among those most likely to be exposed to the virus and to be severely affected by the measures imposed during the lockdown, without receiving any state support (Axelsson et al., 2021). While **the wealthy continued to have access to private hospitals and clinics** offering a wide range of healthcare services, people with low incomes suffered from the consequences of national policies that converted state hospitals into COVID wards. For instance, in Turkey, 'with the policy of turning all public and foundation hospitals into pandemic hospitals, **economic conditions became a determinant of the right to health**. Reports indicate that applications to primary health care and cancer prevention centres declined by 80%, leading to a **rise also in non-COVID related deaths among vulnerable groups**. Overall, both the overburdening of health services with COVID-related emergencies and lockdown measures have prevented people from accessing health services for other health needs' (Cibin et al., 2021).

People suffering from **chronic illnesses, particularly older people and people with disabilities**, became more vulnerable. They 'lost access to rehabilitation services, physical therapy, treatment, as well as communication within their social network' (Cibin et al., 2023). As a consequence, many of them suffered from pandemic-related physical and mental health issues.

While the Eurofund (2021) data analysed in the project point to a significant increase in unmet medical needs across Europe, **a lack of data mean that it is impossible to make a detailed analysis of the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the prevalence of hindered access to treatment and health services for the most marginalised groups**. Much like other areas in which the RESISTIRÉ project is interested, there is little evidence available on the health and wellbeing of non-registered workers, migrants, refugees, and homeless people (Stovell et al., 2021). It is imperative to give a voice to those who are usually forgotten during a crisis and collect more data to provide a better understanding of their unmet medical needs and to identify risks.

Better Stories

- In **Belgium**, the National Intermutual Agency (Collège intermutualiste national) is in charge of implementing a project aimed at improving access to first-line healthcare for vulnerable and isolated groups in deprived neighbourhoods through the outreach work of community health workers (CHW). Around 50 full-time CHWs have been recruited to work in specific deprived urban districts in the country. These CHWs are themselves members of these deprived communities or have an established relationship of trust with, or knowledge of, that community. The profiles of CHWs are varied but the criteria were to hire motivated people, close to the vulnerable groups, with good knowledge of the local neighbourhood and of various languages. The main role of CHWs is to

reach out to the most vulnerable people to put them in contact and build bridges with first-line care services. They have, for example, provided information on vaccination and, in some cases, they have organised vaccinations with local partners. Health is understood as 'wellbeing' and partnerships are developed to ensure that first needs (e.g. a roof) are secure, as this is a precondition for people to start caring about their health.

- In the **Czech Republic**, during the most acute phase of the pandemic, the City of Prague started a project to temporarily convert some hotels into shelters for the majority of the city's homeless people. These six humanitarian hotels had the capacity to accommodate 353 persons and priority was given to people with COVID-19 symptoms, older people, people with a disability, and the seriously ill. A representative of the initiative estimates it helped around 800 people between March 2020 and October 2022. In collaboration with NGOs and CSOs, the offer of stable housing was paired with the provision of individualised medical, social, and legal support. One of these CSOs was *Medici na ulici* (Doctors on the Street), an association of medical students that aims to support homeless people. The possibility of having a single place to interact with these people, coupled with a relationship of trust built over the years between homeless people and these doctors, has made it possible for doctors not only to provide support in relation to COVID-19, but also to address many other problems (e.g. such as parasites, skin infections, etc.). Out of the six hotels established in March 2020, one was designated for homeless women only, providing a safe space for this specific vulnerable group. However, with the rest of the hotels being mixed gender, trans and non-binary homeless people were included as well.
- In **Denmark**, REDEN [The Nest] is a shelter for women in prostitution and dealing with substance abuse issues located in Copenhagen's inner city. Most of the women there have had many bad experiences with the traditional health system and are therefore reluctant to go to its substance treatment centres, and they find it difficult to conform to the rules and regulations and meet the criteria for treatment. With the urgent need to find a solution in the hectic days after the start of lockdown, those responsible for the substance abuse treatment decided to introduce a much more flexible treatment regime: instead of the women having to go to the municipal treatment centres, the treatment left REDEN's premises and went to meet the women where they were. This outreach approach proved to be much more effective because the women felt more secure, and it became easier for the outreach team to build a relationship with them. It suddenly became possible to reach a number of women whom they had previously been unable to help. The new, flexible substance abuse treatment efforts have been such a success that Copenhagen Municipality decided to allocate extra money to this work - initially until the end of 2020, and in municipal budget negotiations this support was then extended to continue to 2024.

1.3 Digital Transformation for an Inclusive Post-COVID Recovery

The sudden acceleration of the digitalisation of public services, healthcare, work, education, and overall human interactions caused by the pandemic response has had an unequivocal impact on people's lives and especially on those most vulnerable.

On the one hand, digital acceleration created conditions for the formation of new inequalities and for the reproduction of existing ones, as many people were excluded from access to the tools and the knowledge required to utilise them and were therefore also excluded from the benefits of the digital transformation.

On the other hand, digital acceleration allowed people and communities to stay connected in a time of physical (social) distancing; it facilitated the continuation of activities carried out by civil society; it made some public services more accessible; and it provided an opportunity to re-think digital inclusion and the role of digital technologies in times of crises.

Recommendations

We recommend that policymakers ensure access to digital infrastructure and competence development. We specifically encourage:

- The development of education programmes and curricula for the enhancement of digital literacy and digital skills, while considering intersecting factors of income and educational levels, geographical positionality, and age, ethnicity, disabilities, and gender in their development;
- The assurance of equality in terms of the availability and affordability of digital infrastructure and connectivity, and doing so by addressing especially rural and urban divides and socioeconomic status;
- The funding of upskilling and reskilling programmes that help displaced workers find new job opportunities, while considering especially existing and intersecting inequalities in relation to age, ethnicity, disabilities, and gender.

We recommend that policymakers consider equity and inclusiveness to be the most important cornerstones of digital policy decision-making and support for digital innovation. We specifically encourage:

- The promotion of policies to support collaborative and co-creative programmes and projects with the aim of developing ethically robust, reliable, and inclusive technologies;
- The development of holistic government approaches to inclusive digital policy- and decision-making and the promotion of cooperation between different ministries in order to address the complexity and inter-relatedness of policy areas influenced by digital transformation;

- The development of policy mechanisms to promote collaboration and exchange between different governmental entities, policy areas, business sectors, and civil society organisations to ensure that digital equality and inclusive digitalisation are promoted within and across sectors;
- The promotion of European cooperation, cross-border information sharing, and closer collaboration with the private sector to minimise the risks of countries falling behind in the digital economy.

We recommend that policymakers intensify their efforts to explore the structural and systemic causes of widening digital inequalities in society. We specifically encourage policymakers to:

- Go beyond removing barriers and focusing on fixing specific groups of people. Digitalisation should be understood as an opportunity to review systems and policies in place and make them more inclusive beyond particular groups or characteristics. This would create room for new ways of mitigating and addressing existing inequalities beyond the digital divide.
- Challenge preconceived and un-reflexive assumptions about user groups in digital innovation and development. When digital solutions are implemented, the question of *who may* and *who may not* benefit from them needs to be given serious consideration. This goes beyond the question of who has access, as the consequences of digitalisation also vary depending on needs.
- Challenge the narrative of digitalisation as a 'universal good'. When digitalisation is treated as an end goal in its own right, rather than as a means to an end, it leaves the potentially harmful effects of digitalisation unaddressed.

Problem Statement

What is the problem with digital inclusion?

During the COVID-19 pandemic, rapid digitalisation shed a light on the problem of vulnerable groups and their access to and use of digital technologies. Billions of people across the globe went online to stay connected, yet almost half of the world's population lacked internet access at the beginning of the crisis (World Economic Forum, 2020). Even in Europe, which in many cases digitally outperforms other parts of the world, rapid digitalisation proved to be unequal: almost half of the EU population lacked basic skills and 20% had none at all. Large differences were also found in terms of major intra- and cross-country disparities in Internet access and digital skills, especially between North-Western Europe and the other regions. These differences also reflect existing societal inequalities, where people who are younger, more educated, male, live in urban regions, and are either students or employed, have better internet access and digital skills than other demographic groups (van Kessel et al., 2022). This tendency, where groups of people already privileged in other respects are also digitally privileged, is of major concern, since it reinforces and widens gaps related not only to what has been

called the first two levels of digital inequalities (internet access and digital skills) but also to a third source of inequalities - the tangible and beneficial outcomes from digital usage.

The consequences of the digital divide and its relation to existing societal inequalities is, however, less discussed (van Kessel et al., 2022; Lutz, 2019). In recent decades, many governments across Europe have stepped up their efforts to promote the availability of digital technologies and build digital skills, with large improvement being observed in these areas. This development can lead to a false impression that the problem of digital inequalities has been fixed, while overlooking the considerable remaining gaps resulting from the intersecting factors of age, income, ethnicity, disabilities, and gender. The pandemic presented a window of opportunity to rethink the use of digital technologies in everyday life and highlighted the potential of digitalisation to address societal inequalities (Perruzzo & Allan, 2022). It is necessary to ensure that the lessons learned during the crisis will guide post-pandemic digitalisation policies.

Insights from RESISTIRÉ

The importance of digital transformation in the post-pandemic recovery

As one of the six pillars of the EU Recovery and Resilience Facility, digital transformation is a central part of the recovery strategy. Among the expenditures outlined in the **National Recovery and Resilience Plans (NRRPs)**, 20% had to be allocated to addressing **the challenges and opportunities of digital transition** (European Commission, 2021a). The NRRPs were mapped in the second cycle of RESISTIRÉ (Cibin et al., 2022; see also RESISTIRÉ Factsheet Nos. 12 and 13). The analysis found that the NRRPs tended to treat digitalisation as a universal good, whereas the potential downsides were rarely mentioned. When the NRRPs did address digital inequalities, the solutions were mostly designed to provide **women and specific vulnerable groups with digital skills, devices, and infrastructures**. The root causes of digital inequalities were usually left unacknowledged. Although gender equality was established as a cross-cutting priority for the NRRPs, it was often poorly understood and implemented, including in the parts dealing with the digital transition. While many measures were aimed at supporting women's access to the digital areas of employment, the NRRPs raise the question of what is *deprioritised* when substantial funds are earmarked for (ostensibly gender-neutral) digitalisation. The overriding risk of most national recovery and resilience plans was that tech sectors - dominated by men - would be funded at the expense of sectors dominated by women, such as the care sector.

The challenges of the omnipresence of technology: the creation of new divides

As seen in the NRRPs, digital inclusion is often seen as a universal good that will be beneficial to all, including vulnerable groups. The negative effects of digitalisation,

including its potentially negative impact on gendered and intersectional equality, are given considerably less attention. Digital inequality is often intertwined with other inequalities in society relating to age, disabilities, migration, socioeconomic background, and geographical location. Data from RESISTIRÉ show how digitalisation during the pandemic increased inequalities in many ways, such as widening already existing gaps in education between children from different socioeconomic households (see RESISTIRÉ Factsheet No. 11), increasing unpaid work hours for women when hybrid work was introduced (see RESISTIRÉ Factsheet No. 7), or generating new means of control and abuse (see RESISTIRÉ Factsheet No. 10). Other negative effects highlighted by RESISTIRÉ's data include the spread of misinformation online, the use of digital technology for surveillance, and the loss of valuable aspects of service provision when the service is moved online (Sandström et al., 2023). While some digital inequalities can be mitigated by ensuring that digital tools and the competence to use them are freely available to all, what these negative impacts show is that the 'solution' may not always be digital. When digitalisation is promoted uncritically, this point is rarely considered.

While the examples given below focus primarily on the digitalisation of public services, it should be noted that the risk of negative, and unequal, effects is apparent in other areas as well. The rapid digitalisation of the labour market is particularly noteworthy. Digitalisation experts consulted in RESISTIRÉ's research highlighted that a significant share of the population is at risk of exclusion from the labour market as digital skills are now deemed to be as essential as basic literacy and numeracy skills. Over 90% of professional roles already require some digital skills, and because digitalisation has spread far beyond traditional office jobs nearly all jobs may soon require some digital skills (European Commission, 2022a).

- Unequal access to essential services

During the pandemic the need and demand for welfare services remained or even increased. This encompasses the provision of a wide range of public services, from health and education to policing and other social services. Interviews with street-level civil servants highlighted how **the rapid digitalisation of public service provision was not equally beneficial to all** and that the majority of those for whom digital technologies are designed have certain digital privileges. Access to services for those not in this privileged position was severely hampered as a result of several factors: poor infrastructure, especially in rural areas; digital systems that were not inclusive or user-friendly; the use of exclusionary language in digital applications; the considerable cost of broadband and digital devices; and the lack of opportunities for developing digital competence.

Equal access to essential public services is a human right⁸ and when some groups lack the digital equipment and skills required to access public services, **digital exclusion becomes a human rights violation**. Since digital inequalities intertwine with other inequalities, those most in need of access are often also the ones most at risk of having their rights denied. Rapid Assessment Surveys across Europe revealed increased digital inequalities during the pandemic (Harroche et al., 2023). For instance, **accessing digital resources and knowing how to use them** was a key issue during lockdowns that **impeded older people's access to information, services, and social contacts**. Many older people were unable to book COVID-19 vaccination appointments as often the only way to do so was through an online booking system, while **economically marginalised groups** were **excluded from social benefits as online registration was required**.

Education was another area where digitalisation led to increased inequalities (Sandström et al., 2022). The woman quoted below lived as an asylum seeker in Sweden during the pandemic and her story illuminates how asylum seekers, whose rights to education were already severely restricted, were pushed further into the margins. Whereas adult asylum seekers rely on civil society initiatives to meet their education needs, minors have a formal right to education. However, due to the pandemic both her own and her teenage son's access to education was restricted:

All classes were cancelled due to COVID. They said I could study using WhatsApp, but that did not work for me at all. It is just not the same as sitting next to a teacher and having them explain things to you. I think I understood maybe 20% of the online classes ... I am sure I would have progressed much further if it had not been for COVID and online teaching.

Access to the internet was another huge obstacle. Every month we bought 200 minutes of phone credit and 3 GB of data each ... My son sometimes had to do online classes as well and one time he ran out of data in the middle of a lesson. I called the Migration Agency asking for help. They put me on hold, and after 15 minutes my phone credit ran out. (refugee woman aged 34, Sweden)

- Digitalisation and the impact on the quality of services

The quote above highlight how the cost of broadband can prevent access to services, but it also raises the question of whether the same *quality* of service can be provided through digital means. Studies indicate that the quality of education declined during the pandemic: over one-half of respondents in the Global Survey on 'Youth and COVID-19' (ILO, 2020) reported to have learnt less since the start of the pandemic. This could

⁸ Article 21 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/universal-declaration-of-human-rights>

perhaps be explained by the rapid pace of digitalisation and the lack of preparedness, but the RESISTIRÉ data also show that **schools have an important social function** that is difficult to replicate digitally. **Many students suffered mentally** from the lack of peer support when education was moved online and teachers reported that it was harder to establish a **social connection with students**, making it more **difficult to identify students in need of extra support**. Additionally, for some children schools provide a **safe space away from a difficult home environment**, and this, too, was lost when remote education was introduced.

- Misinformation, mistrust, and surveillance

Qualitative RESISTIRÉ data also show that **misinformation online was a widespread** problem during the pandemic (Sandström et al., 2022; Sandström et al., 2023). Although the development of digital competence and critical thinking skills are important tools in determining the trustworthiness of information sources, the inclination of many to deliberately seek out alternatives to information provided by public authorities needs to be taken seriously. In some instances, this inclination was based on a well-founded **distrust of public authorities**. A **fear of surveillance**, whether well-founded or not, could also lead to a **reluctance to engage with digitalisation**. Authoritative control measures implemented during the pandemic, often using digital technology as a tool, helped reinforce this sense of distrust. The quote below, from a Cypriot woman, illustrates this point:

I felt uncomfortable with one incident during the lockdown when we were forced to send text messages to be able to leave the house. We were allowed to send 2 SMS per day. We sent one SMS to go to the fields to cut the oranges ... So we went in the morning and naturally this job lasted more than the 3-hour 'unwritten rule' for each message. When we were returning home a police officer stopped our car and accused us of using the SMS the wrong way because he said that a whole day of work in the fields was not a 'reasonable amount of time'. We started arguing and shouting and this made my husband and I feel very bad ... I believe this is a dark area and obstruction of our human rights of freedom of movement due to the wrong interpretation of government measures. (woman aged 65, Cyprus)

Digitalisation as an opportunity for inclusion

The pandemic showed that when crisis responses are digitalised, this creates the risk of excluding large portions of already vulnerable groups. However, RESISTIRÉ's findings also highlighted instances where digitalisation had unintended positive effects on inequalities and revealed multitude innovative ways in which it was used for the purpose of closing inequality gaps (Sandström et al., 2023; Cibin et al., 2023). These findings show how important it is not only to see decreasing digital inequalities as an end goal

but also to recognise how digitalisation can in fact be used as a tool to address broader social inequalities.

- Improved conditions for service provision

In interviews with street-level civil servants, they highlighted several ways in which digitalisation could lead to more inclusive services. Some of the examples they gave related specifically to the importance of digital solutions for **keeping services going during a crisis**. For instance, online classes allowed students to keep up with their education despite the lockdowns, and hybrid activities allowed older people to participate in sports classes. However, moving activities online could also make services more inclusive in the long run and street-level civil servants reported that digital consultations had proved beneficial for some clients as they enabled **greater access to public services for clients living on the outskirts of the city**. Digitalisation also improved communication in some instances. Using computer-generated SMS messages made it **easier for service providers to reach clients**, and other digital tools became useful instruments for **maintaining contact with the victims of gender-based violence**. Finally, the street-level civil servants found that **digitalisation allowed them to save time** on some tasks, whereby they were able to spend more time providing services.

Representatives from civil society organisations also described some aspects of digitalisation as beneficial on the organisational level and, as a consequence, it in a wider sense supported their work in tackling inequalities (Cibin et al., 2023). They, too, found that digitalisation could save time that could be used in a more productive way, as exemplified in the quote below from a representative of a Turkish civil society organisation:

Since our work has been more digitalised with the development of a database with all the necessary data regarding the beneficiaries, we no longer have to spend too much time on the operation and delivery of in-kind support. Hence, we can spend more time on monitoring households and measuring the impact of our work, maintaining good relationships with individual donors (80% of the initiative's financial resources come from individual donors), and swiftly mobilising resources and channelling them to beneficiaries. (CSO representative, Turkey)

Several representatives of civil society organisations reported that digitalisation had improved work processes and the internal sharing of information among organisations. Like the street-level civil servants, the representatives of civil society organisations also saw digitalisation as a means of **overcoming mobility-related and geographical barriers** and as a means of **improving communication**. Digitalisation made communication with various stakeholders easier and it enabled users to keep in touch with their initiatives and with other users. The representatives of civil society

organisations also reported that digitalisation had enabled them to **create resilient networks** and it had increased opportunities for **advocacy and awareness raising**.

- The future is hybrid

Narrative interviews with members of marginalised groups showed that while the quality of the service sometimes declined, some interviewees actually stated **a preference for services provided online**. One example is provided by an Estonian student with an anxiety disorder and agoraphobia, whose appointments with her therapist and her psychiatrist were moved online during the pandemic, and she spoke of this change in positive terms:

I managed to check in even if I was feeling terrible; surely if I had had to leave home at this point, I just would not have showed up. I realised that when I do physically show up in their space, it is more difficult to refrain from crying but actually easier to make myself 'feel different' - I can fake it better, just as I do in real-life social situations to appear more socially acceptable and do the visit in the right way. On Zoom, I was much more able to focus on myself, to notice where I was and what I was feeling. (student aged 18, Estonia)

The importance of hybrid solutions has been a key message throughout the RESISTIRÉ project and a final quote from a representative of one civil society organisation shows that in order to achieve an inclusive post-COVID recovery through digital transformation, we need to find the right **balance between the digital and the non-digital**, always taking the needs of the individual into account:

We will not completely return to where we were more than 2 years ago. Many sources of access for some women have been improved; many benefits arose during that time. However, online counselling is not always the only method. For example, there is the possibility of a combination of face-to-face and online counselling. Counsellors can consider together with the client which counselling method is best for the particular combination. (CSO representative, Germany)

Better Stories

Lithuania ranks among the countries in which schools were closed the longest during the pandemic. During the first period of remote learning, a number of problems emerged: despite distributing 35 000 additional computers to schools, some children still lacked access to computers and the Internet; children who lived in small dwellings did not have proper space in which to participate in education; some parents lacked computer skills and could not help their children; computer/software infrastructure in schools was insufficient or outdated; and not all teachers were qualified to work with

remote learning platforms. For this reason, a specific policy was put in place that aimed to support those who were digitally excluded, while also taking into account the broad ecosystem of needs that the education system caters to. The policy allowed children from socially underprivileged backgrounds and those without an appropriate home environment in which to learn to be taught remotely in schools using school infrastructure, but it also set out other related measures: the children received care and food services after classes; schools were provided with laptops that could be used for socially vulnerable children's remote schooling; individual consultations were offered to children with learning difficulties; and volunteers from NGOs were included to assist with the learning process at educational institutions.

In Finland⁹, during the lockdown phases, the NGO 'Kansallinen senioriliitto ry' (the National Association of Senior Citizens) created different online activities to keep its members in contact and to prevent isolation. First, the NGO launched a new podcast series, which discussed the life of senior people during the pandemic. Then, since the association's members were spending a lot of time at home and could not meet each other as usual, their meetings were organised online through meeting platforms. For this reason, the NGO trained 33 'platform representatives' to create, help, and support the implementation of remote meetings and activities in circles and associations using online platforms. In this way, seniors quickly adapted to new technologies.

In Poland, the Association of Deaf People developed a video helpline to support its members. Translators of Polish Sign Language from all over Poland were involved in the initiative. They worked in shifts on smartphones or laptops with Internet access. A deaf person could call the helpline to obtain information about the coronavirus and how to proceed in the event of a suspected infection. The helpline could also be used by employees of healthcare facilities and emergency medical services, as it could facilitate medical interviews with deaf patients and accelerate possible diagnosis and treatment.

1.4 Promoting Sustainable and Resilient Long-Term Care

The pandemic had a huge impact on people in need of long-term care (LTC) because of the reduced possibility (or even impossibility) of obtaining the amount of good-quality care they needed during the crisis. At the same time, the pandemic reminded society of the value of our health and care systems, and the essential role performed by people who work as carers, whether they are formally employed in the sector or work informally as unpaid carers. Despite this, not enough attention was paid during the pandemic to the issue of how to make LTC systems more resilient, while the negative effects of the crisis on both carers and the people

⁹ <https://www.sttinfo.fi/tiedote/senioreiden-kansalaisjarjesto-on-tehnyt-komeita-digiloikkia-korona-kevaan-aikana-seniori-podcast-teams-palavereita-ja-youtubessa-rappia?publisherId=69817593&releasId=69884285>

being cared for are likely to persist (if not worsen) in the coming years if no action is taken.

Recommendations

Improve the quality of formal care and ensure the resilience of the care sector during crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic

The [European Care Strategy](#) presented by the European Commission in September 2022 is aimed at ensuring the accessibility, affordability, and quality of care services across EU countries and at improving the situation of both the recipients of care and (formal and informal) carers. While the strategy includes a [Council Recommendation](#) on access to affordable high-quality LTC, more work should be done to highlight the importance of a **care system that is resilient** to external shocks. One point already raised in the Recommendation is to make the **profession of care worker more attractive** and to do so by improving working conditions and making the profession more gender-balanced. Initiatives at the local level can be promoted, for example, by **involving students** (especially those in the fields of medicine, healthcare, care) in care-related activities and building a **better working environment**, so that formal carers are not burdened with too many responsibilities. **More recognition should be given to the profession of care worker** on different levels (economic, cultural, social).

On the supply side, an idea that emerged from one of the RESISTIRÉ pilot projects was to **create a 'quality' label for private care services**. The label would provide a guarantee that private care services bearing the label uphold the rights of domestic care workers and care recipients.

Consolidating a rights-based approach to LTC

A rights-based approach to LTC provides a powerful framework for ensuring equality of access to good-quality LTC services. In order to effectively implement Principle 18 of the European Pillar of Social Rights, the EU is supporting Member States' efforts towards guaranteeing equal access through the provision of LTC services that are affordable and of good quality (see the Council Recommendation on access to affordable, high-quality LTC). However, a **challenge in consolidating a rights-based approach** is how varied the nature and scope of LTC services offered across the EU currently are. **Monitoring Member States' implementation of Council Recommendations, and increasing support efforts when and where needed, will be crucial for overcoming this challenge.**

Value the work of informal care

Policies at the EU level supporting informal care should place a stronger focus on promoting formal recognition of the value of informal care work (mainly carried out by women) with the aim of effectively **supporting the people who perform this work.**

While many initiatives have already been implemented (such as the [Work-Life Balance Directive](#), which introduced carers' leave for workers providing personal care or support to a relative), they may not be sufficient when it comes to the many people who provide LTC informally. While care leave policies help to **ease the burden on working people who are also performing informal care activities, formal support should be extended to all informal carers, irrespective of whether or not they are economically active.**

Identify the most vulnerable groups of care workers and care recipients

Some care workers can be identified as more vulnerable than others because their **working conditions are more difficult** (e.g. live-in carers) or **because they are the subject of intersecting inequality grounds** (e.g. migrant care workers, single mothers), or because of the overlapping of these conditions. The same is true for care recipients, who may find themselves in a position of intersecting inequalities. A **gender+ perspective** should be applied when developing policies to improve the conditions of care workers and care recipients.

Building community care and community resilience and mainstreaming these approaches

Community care refers to any form of care and support provided in the local community that enables people to overcome or manage any condition, disability, or life difficulties they may face. Despite available evidence that community care and resilience create more value for the persons in need of care and for those who provide (informal/formal) care, as well as for society as a whole, such approaches have **not yet been mainstreamed into practice**. Where face-to-face services had to be interrupted during the pandemic to stop the spread of the virus, **voluntary organisations** proved to be very important, because they were able to **provide quick and effective solutions** to meet the needs of more vulnerable groups. Community care can also help to **break care silos**, thereby improving the efficiency of the services offered and increasing **community awareness and solidarity**.

Make sure that CSOs receive adequate funding for their initiatives at the community level

More resources should be allocated to initiatives at the local level that act on both prevention and care, as these initiatives played a fundamental role during the pandemic.

Problem Statement

In the context of population ageing, demand for high-quality LTC is expected to increase in the coming years (European Commission, 2021b). Principle 18 of the European Pillar of Social Rights states that '[e]veryone has the right to affordable long-term care services

of good quality, in particular home care and community-based services' (European Commission, 2018). However, COVID-19 shone a spotlight on the systemic weaknesses of the LTC system, which were manifested through the high mortality rates in residential care facilities, difficulties in guaranteeing the continuity of quality care (both at home and in residential care settings), and the negative impact on the wellbeing of both older people and carers (European Commission, 2021b). In this context, we should not forget that most of the LTC in Europe is provided by informal or unpaid caregivers, who are thus the main suppliers of health and social care to older or disabled people (D'Amen, Soggi & Santini, 2021). The increased burden of care responsibilities that were experienced mainly by female (in)formal caregivers caused them a great amount of stress and exhaustion.

Insights from RESISTIRÉ

- Older adults receiving home care experienced a decline in the quantity and quality of care

Concerns about COVID-19 infection, and the restrictions that were imposed to avoid this risk, led to a decrease in the quantity and quality of the home care, which older adults (especially those over the age of 80) rely on for daily support. Based on RESISTIRÉ's analysis of [SHARE data](#), there were more women than men dependent on home care both before and during the pandemic. From the beginning of the pandemic, both women and men reported **difficulties obtaining the amount of home care** they needed, in most cases because the **carer was unable to come to their home**. An overall improvement was observed in summer 2021, most likely because there were fewer restrictions in place at that time than there were during the first wave of the survey (summer 2020).

The policy and societal initiatives mapped in RESISTIRÉ showed that some countries designed **specific measures to mitigate the difficulties experienced by people with disabilities and older adults**, who were often confined to their homes without assistance when day centres were closed. In **Poland**, for example, people with disabilities were given financial compensation in the form of the co-financing of costs related to the provision of care at home in the event of loss of access to care from a rehabilitation facility and in the form of the increased monthly co-financing of their salaries and compensation for those who are employed in Vocational Activity Establishments'. In **Denmark**, funding was 'allocated to combat loneliness among people with disabilities'. In **Italy**, disability permits were strengthened, together with special funds to increase assistance and services and implement projects for people with very serious disabilities.

- Residents of care facilities were deprived of their autonomy and their rights and dignity were regularly undermined

Because of their higher risk of dying from COVID-19 and the restrictions imposed to reduce the possibility of infection, **older adults living in care homes** were negatively affected in their everyday lives and suffered serious effects from these restrictions. Their suffering was primarily caused by the practical difficulties associated with being **isolated in their rooms** to prevent contagion and by **the ban on visits from family and external friends** (Brooke & Jackson, 2020; Gordon et al., 2020). Many of the experts interviewed by RESISTIRÉ highlighted these difficulties: clients suffering because of the no-visit policy or restricted visits; some clients being confused and unable to recognise staff or family members because of medical protections such as masks or over-the-body covers. As one worker in a residential care home said, the **'human touch' was missing**: *'It was hard that we couldn't help. Even us, we had little time to stay in the room, it was just to give them their tray'* (family assistant working in Belgium). Care home residents described their experience as having to live for many days like **'a prisoner sentenced to solitary confinement'** (72-year-old woman from Croatia). The restrictions on visits to nursing homes and the resulting isolation created a feeling of loneliness among those who were living in care facilities, but also among the relatives who were not allowed to visit their loved ones: *'I could not touch or hug my parents and I lost my freedom. too. Calling my family and friends [...] helped me with my loneliness, but **I still missed the physical aspect**'* (59-year-old woman in the Netherlands).

- Care workers were at risk of burnout as a result of numerous overtime shifts, stress, and fatigue

The pandemic and the policy responses to it had a significant impact on the sphere of care work, with care workers being more likely to be exposed to the virus, suffering various physical conditions as a result of their heavy workload, and often experiencing anxiety, stress, and depression, without receiving any state support. As a consequence, they became a **new vulnerable group**. The conditions were particularly difficult for care workers with multiple or intersecting inequalities, such as **sex and ethnicity**. As highlighted by experts in the project's interviews, migrant women care workers, who were already in a precarious situation before the pandemic (for example because they were single mothers, women 50+, or women in a difficult financial situation), had to deal with the **fear of losing their job and income**, as well as **worries about their family health and safety back home**. As reported by one person working as caregiver far away from her home country:

*'I stayed with my client for a long time, which came with a massive physical and mental burden. [...] During that time, I was constantly under pressure. Even when my mother passed away, I did not take the time to mourn. [...] **Living with my client felt like "a prison to me"**. My client felt the same way, he often missed his family.'* (50-year-old woman living in Austria)

- The burden of informal care fell primarily on women, with detrimental consequences for their work-life balance and mental and physical health

People who needed long-term care and were unable to receive home care had to rely on the support of relatives for this task. Most informal long-term care for older adults in Europe continues to be provided by **middle-aged women**; however, **younger adults** are taking up an increasing share of care responsibilities as a result of labour market and family changes (D'Amen, Socci & Santini, 2021). Ample evidence has shown that **caregiving** has a significant impact on the mental health of the carers (Hoyt et al., 2021), their wellbeing (Hamilton & Adamson, 2013), and their ability to balance work and care duties in everyday life (ME-WE Consortium, 2019). Emerging evidence from the pandemic confirms that there was an increase in **mental health inequalities** among **young adult carers** of ill parents or family members compared to non-carers (Landi et al., 2022), most likely related to factors such as increased social isolation, school closures, and concerns about the health of the care recipients and their family's economic situation (King, 2021).

Increased care responsibilities – **especially among women** – during the pandemic as a result of school closures and the loss of formal and informal support were reported both in the RAS mapped by RESISTIRÉ throughout the three cycles and in the narratives of respondents recorded during the research, such as the experience of a 68-year-old woman in Poland:

*'Three days a week I care for my mother who lives far away. I combine professional work with caring for my mother and my daughter. **Caring for my mother is very challenging, physically and mentally tiring, and time consuming.** It is hard to work afterwards. My mother [...] has a serious disability and requires 24/7 care. [...] I have two other female carers who support me in care when I am away. Our caring plans changed due to the pandemic. We already had a situation where one of the carers became infected with the coronavirus and [...] I constantly had to take her place and care for my mother.'*

- The importance of community for care and the role of technology

Neighbourhoods and local communities can provide a great sense of mutual support among people, and the importance of living in a caring and supportive environment was a recurring theme in the narratives collected by RESISTIRÉ. Community-level initiatives played a fundamental role for people living alone who needed help with basic daily activities such as buying groceries, as reported by a woman living alone:

*'The **neighbourhood was really good.** The neighbours were very*

friendly towards me. After my husband died, they often, despite the fear of contagion, came knocking on my door to ask how I was. [...] With another lady, we have another habit that started during COVID. On Tuesdays, we go to a distant supermarket for discount day. We go together in her car.’ (80-year-old woman in Italy)

Technology seems to have played a fundamental role in maintaining contact among neighbours, as demonstrated by the experiences of many people interviewed who mentioned that they used WhatsApp groups to stay in touch with other people and to make sure that those in need could be helped:

*‘We have a WhatsApp group with the neighbours, and during the lockdown we went to the window clapping, but **we also cooked for each other and left the food on the doorstep as a gift.** We already had a great relationship, but it grew even stronger. We are always ready to help each other. These bonds that were established in such a difficult time are of great importance.’ (66-year-old woman in Spain)*

However, social media and technology were not always effective at reaching the people most in need, as reported in one narrative:

‘Many people offered their help [in an app for neighbours], and some found help. However, many who would have needed help probably were not able to find it. I think it is very important to find other ways to connect people with others who live near them. If everyone had a few phone numbers of neighbours they know they can call for help and support, this would create a lot of resilience during a crisis. I understand that people are hesitant to connect with their neighbours because they don’t want to lose their anonymity in the neighbourhood.’ (51-year-old woman in Finland)

Better Stories

Outdoor concerts organised at care homes for older adults (Netherlands)

In the Netherlands, a small local organisation arranged more than 250 outdoor concerts at care homes for older adults between March and September 2020. The events were co-organised by cultural and art institutions, care institutions, and the residents themselves. After the lockdown brought a sudden halt to activities, the organisation came up with the idea of giving concerts outside, so that residents could still enjoy activities through the window. What began as a local initiative became a national one, as the organisation issued a call on social media to anyone interested in participating in the initiative and were able to reach many artists and other care facilities.

Improving working conditions for domestic workers: 'Allied Employers' (Spain)

The idea for this pilot action stemmed from the recognition that the working conditions of the most marginalised and vulnerable care workers working in private households were largely neglected during the pandemic. The project was developed by the SOS Racismo Gipuzkoa organisation based in the Basque Country and was aimed at mobilising employers of domestic workers, raising their awareness of domestic workers' rights and needs, highlighting the importance of acting as allies, strengthening the voices of migrant women domestic workers, and informing other employers and the public of the project's results. The project created a safe space for dialogue between domestic workers and employers, in which a list of shared proposals for the improvement of the sector was developed (see Recommendations). These proposals were presented to municipal and provincial institutions, and an awareness-raising campaign was created to present the project's results to the stakeholders involved in the process and to the public. [Find out more here.](#)

Connecting neighbours with each other: 'Nappi Naapuri' service (Finland)

Nappi Naapuri is a social web service focused on local cooperation, where everyone can send messages on a neighbourhood map and answer to other people's messages. The platform is designed to promote neighbourly help and create a positive community of neighbours, with the aim of increasing social capital and employing proximity as a common resource. During the pandemic, a special [Corona Help category](#) was quickly launched, and many people joined the platform to offer help (such as shopping) to those neighbours in vulnerable positions. [Find out more here.](#)

1.5 Addressing Poverty and Social Exclusion: A Feminist Perspective

With multiple crises impacting the global economy, more and more people are being pushed or pushed harder into poverty. According to the UN (2022), COVID-19 caused the first increase in poverty rates in decades. Lockdowns introduced at different phases of the pandemic led to job losses and consequent losses of income, accommodation, and financial independence. It has been shown that groups at various intersections of inequality and particularly gender, class, age, and nationality were made even more vulnerable and pushed into deep poverty during the crisis.

Civil society organisations (CSOs), feminist organisations, and other initiatives played a key role in reaching out to the margins and supporting vulnerable groups who fell through the cracks of social protection schemes. Their creative strategies for fighting poverty along intersecting inequalities should be harnessed in the future to ensure a feminist and human rights approach.

Background Information

The pandemic deepened existing inequalities and disproportionately affected women, particularly those from marginalised communities. A feminist approach recognises the intersectionality of gender with other social inequalities based on race, class, ethnicity, and disability, among others, and understands that addressing poverty requires an understanding of the unique challenges faced by different groups of women.

According to EAPN data in Spain, for example, 13.1 million people are at risk of poverty or exclusion due to the COVID-19 crisis. The ILO (2021a) has confirmed that ‘women have suffered **disproportionate job and income losses** because of their over-representation in the hardest-hit sectors’, and the job growth observed in 2021 would be insufficient to bring women’s employment back to pre-pandemic employment levels. The **reduction in women’s paid work has also been connected to an increase in their share of unpaid work**, as Mascherini and Nivakoski (2021) have suggested. Another factor that is associated with an increased risk of poverty is single parenthood. Poverty rates have been found to be particularly higher for single mothers in OECD countries compared to single fathers (Zagel, Hübgen & Nieuwenhuis, 2021). While **emergency social protection measures** were effective at ensuring an income for large portions of the population during the lockdowns and the resulting economic crisis, **many of the most disadvantaged groups of people fell through the cracks in the system. Atypical workers and people in non-formal employment** were among those excluded from protection mechanisms.

Recommendations for Policymakers

Addressing poverty and social exclusion through a human rights approach

Adopting a holistic and human rights approach to address poverty and social exclusion is crucial for fighting poverty and creating a more just and equitable society. As underlined in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (SDG1), ending poverty and social exclusion requires efforts at both the national and the European level. The short- and long-term impacts of the pandemic support the adoption of a rights-based European Poverty Strategy backed by European funds (Malgesini, 2021). In line with the recommendations delivered by the UN Special Rapporteur on Extreme Poverty and Human Rights (2022), RESISTIRÉ recommends that policymakers:

- Address poverty through a **human rights-based approach** to build resilience among communities before a crisis takes place, following the guiding principles adopted by the UN Human Rights Council (21/11) in 2012.
- **Render social protection schemes inclusive and accessible to all.** While avoiding legal exclusions, efforts should be directed at reducing the ‘non-take-up’ of social protection among eligible groups by reducing bureaucracy and

eliminating any other barriers, including the digital gap, stigmatisation, and institutional discrimination;

- Adopt policies with a **gender+ approach**, ensuring that those groups that are at a higher risk of poverty, such as women, youth, and migrants, have effective access to social protection.
- **Foster a broad ecosystem of services** that guarantee access to health, food, education, housing, socialisation, and political representation. This requires that policies be built through **multi-sectoral collaboration**. When making decisions about suspending or closing these services in times of crisis, it is essential to also keep in mind secondary consequences and long-term consequences (Cibin et al., 2023), especially for those groups that are at a higher risk of poverty, such as women and youth, including LGBTQI+ youth.
- **Prepare crisis intervention plans**, which set out in advance what urgent actions need to be taken in order to protect people at risk of poverty, such as: **eviction bans** due to non-payment of rents and mortgages, **energy bill payment support**, and continued **provision of free school meals**.

Improving outreach and activating local communities to build resilience

For a change of paradigm to be effective, cooperation should be established between local authorities and communities to improve outreach strategies, **address emerging needs**, and **identify crisis-specific risk-factors**:

- To reach out to the most vulnerable communities, local authorities should establish **cooperation with the local stakeholders, CSOs, and communities** that are best placed to engage with people on the margins and identify their changing needs.
- When setting up policies that impact the most vulnerable, it is **essential to involve those CSOs that interact with vulnerable groups at risk of poverty in the policy-making and decision-making process, and make sure to include diverse and intersectional voices**. It is essential to adopt a gender+ perspective to ensure those groups who are at a higher risk of poverty can benefit from support.
- CSOs play an important role in fighting poverty. **Increasing public funding to support their activities** and **reducing the bureaucratic burden** would allow them to sustain their work and reach the most vulnerable groups. Nonetheless, CSOs should not be confined to the role of service providers and should not be substitutes for the relevant authorities who are responsible for providing services.

Improve intersectional data collection

Policy actions should be informed and evidence-based, which is why it is crucial to formulate research questions that address different and intersecting inequality grounds.

The COVID-19 pandemic showed that the groups affected most can also be the ones that are the most difficult to reach. The collection of data on these groups was affected by the pandemic. For instance, restrictive measures meant that many surveys had to be conducted online, and many people in these groups had limited access to the internet, so data on their situation were not collected (Harroche et al., 2023). Analyses of different RAS show that to ensure that data collection is carried out with a conscious intersectional approach, it should be designed in a way that is **as accessible and inclusive as possible and engages with different stakeholders** (e.g. CSOs, authorities involved in service delivery).

Recommendations for Civil Society Organisations

Investing in digital skills and increasing digital literacy

CSOs and initiatives had to move some of their operations online during the crisis to continue their work safely and effectively, and this allowed them also to increase their contact with different stakeholders and beneficiaries. In the process, they also increased their digital literacy. This is an improvement they can benefit from in the management of future crises as well as in their daily operations. To this end, it is imperative for CSOs to commit to continuous learning and to upskilling their staff members in digital knowledge.

Engaging beneficiaries as active agents

The CSOs involved in RESISTIRÉ's research pointed out that engaging beneficiaries in their larger work **improves the quality of their response** to poverty that results from multiple axes of inequality and vulnerability as well as crisis conditions. The representatives of the CSOs also highlighted the significance of **participatory processes** and creating space for beneficiaries to become active agents. This also helps in moving away from the charity mindset. One example mapped by RESISTIRÉ was a neighbourhood platform created in a low-income district in Madrid (Spain), in which 800 neighbours became involved in several food banks and support groups. Stress was also placed on the importance of involving stakeholders in **advocacy work**.

Maintaining networks of solidarity and collaboration

In an effort to address the inequalities that emerged and were exacerbated during the pandemic, respond inclusively to the needs of people in poverty, and manage the crisis, initiatives had to **mobilise networks of solidarity and collaboration with other CSOs, private companies, local authorities, local people, and others**. This involved collaborating with already established networks and alliances, as well as mobilising solidarity, cooperating with other stakeholders, and developing skills to assess the impact of collective action. It is crucial to keep these networks alive and find ways to sustain and foster long-term solidarity and collaboration.

Insights from RESISTIRÉ

Segmented approaches to poverty

Tackling poverty and unemployment was an issue addressed in the majority of National Recovery and Resilience Plans, but the **gender+ dimension of poverty is almost entirely absent** (Cibin et al., 2022).

Even prior to the pandemic, **women were at a higher risk of poverty**, as they tend to be employed in low-income and precarious sectors, and the gender care gap often hinders their participation in the labour market. **Children and parents in single-headed households** faced an increased risk of food deprivation as a result of their increased risk of poverty and job loss. National Surveys mapped by RESISTIRÉ found that ‘the greatest impacts on women’s income and employment were primarily linked to women’s increased caring duties due to offices and schools closing. This increase was steeper among lone parents, but also applied to families with both parents at home’ (Stovell et al., 2021).

Young people aged 16-24 also reported more difficulties making ends meet, probably because they were more likely to be working in precarious jobs and in sectors that were unable to operate during the pandemic (e.g. retail and service industries). Regardless of age, women reported more financial difficulties, which may be linked to a gender gap in pensions (Stovell et al., 2021; European Commission, 2020). A French survey on poverty levels found that women and young people were the two groups most likely to restrict the amount and quality of the food they eat because of income loss (Stovell et al., 2021).

In many countries, measures were gradually introduced to mitigate the effects of workplace closures, mobility restrictions, and rising unemployment, but they often targeted specific sectors and segments of the population, whereas **workers in non-formal or atypical employment fell through the cracks** in the system (Cibin et al., 2021; Stovell et al., 2021). Migrant women working in the care sector, undocumented migrant workers, sex workers, and workers in other informally organised sub-fields ended up in an extremely vulnerable position as a result of the pandemic. Excluded from social protection, these groups resorted to the help of civil society initiatives, which saw an increased demand for basic products such as food, hygiene products, medicines, and support to pay the rent. In some cases, the national authorities provided special funding for non-profit organisations and municipalities working on the provision of basic needs to vulnerable groups, but these were temporary and exceptional.

The role of social protection in addressing poverty

Some national recovery plans contain measures to improve and expand social housing (Italy, Slovenia), increase and adjust social security benefits (Croatia, Estonia), improve the Minimum Income Scheme (Spain, Romania, Greece, Bulgaria, Latvia, Lithuania), and promote lifelong education and the re/upskilling of long-term unemployed persons (Czech Republic, Ireland, Croatia, Belgium). Moreover, recovery plans promised to tackle socioeconomic inequalities in access to education by supporting schools in disadvantaged territories (Portugal, Czech Republic, Germany), targeting low-income, single-headed families and migrant and Roma families (Spain), equipping schools with digital infrastructure and tools (Poland), and distributing these tools among students (Ireland, Austria).

However, CSOs have argued that such measures are still insufficient and not properly funded. It is important that in the current implementation phase, gender-sensitive monitoring and evaluation is carried out, particularly to understand the gender+ impact of these plans and who was left out of them.

Access to education and health for the most vulnerable

People living in poverty and social exclusion often experience **lower accessibility to quality health services and adequate accommodation and inequality in their educational process**. While limited information is available on the inequalities in access to healthcare that occurred during the pandemic, data collected through RESISTIRÉ indicate that difficulties were faced particularly by groups at the intersection between socioeconomic disadvantage and gender, migrant background, age, and sexual orientation (see RESISTIRÉ Factsheet No. 14 on Access to Health Services for Vulnerable Groups). The lockdown and the closure of schools forced activities to be moved online, and children from low-income families faced several barriers in their home-schooling experience, ranging from the lack of an adequate space to study, due to overcrowded houses, to the lack of a computer or an internet connection (see RESISTIRÉ Factsheet No. 11 on Developing Resilient Education Systems).

The role of CSOs in reaching out to the most marginalised groups: addressing needs and making them visible

CSOs have been facing increasing demands for basic needs (including food, medicines, housing, hygiene products) from people already living in a precarious situation, but also from people who experienced financial difficulties for the first time due to the pandemic. While struggling with limited funding, an increasing workload, changing restrictions, and bureaucratic barriers, CSOs managed to address these needs, fill the gaps left by insufficient social protection measures, and organise **quick and flexible responses**, such as collecting essential goods and food and distributing them to disadvantaged people and their children. They were also able to do crowdfunding to make up for the lack of economic income for sex workers, artists, domestic workers, and small businesses, and they carried out research and assistance activities relating to situations

of poverty and respect for human rights. Societal initiatives also included mutual aid platforms to help people in isolated situations obtain access to goods and services (Cibin et al., 2023).

CSOs played a key role in **reaching out to and recording the experiences** of the most marginalised groups, thereby making their situation more visible. The limited amount of data available for conducting an intersectional analysis is a problem that was repeatedly highlighted during our research, which points to the importance of oversampling certain groups but also of engaging stakeholders like CSOs or public authorities to help increase the engagement of hard-to-reach groups, such as people living in poverty (see RESISTIRÉ Factsheet No. 21 on More Intersectional Data).

Better Stories

- **In Turkey, the ‘Deep Poverty Network’** was founded as a research and reading group to investigate the deepening of poverty, give visibility to its multidimensional nature, develop a rights-based approach to poverty, and monitor the human rights of the socioeconomically marginalised. The conditions of poverty exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic and the economic downturn led the initiative to broaden its activities, mainly by providing food support to families who had limited access to food during the pandemic. With its effective advocacy work on poverty as a basic human-rights issue and widespread rights-based solidarity campaigns during the pandemic, it has become the most visible civil society initiative on poverty in Turkey. Current activities include (1) research and advocacy; (2) in-kind support via solidarity campaigns; and (3) social work through neighbourhood and home visits to monitor daily living conditions and needs and to facilitate social service support (from municipalities or public institutions). The initiative’s database currently contains 1000 families; 200-300 of them are monitored regularly, 60 of which are led by single women.
- **In Spain, the ‘Lehen Urratsa’ programme** was launched by the Basque government after the lockdown to support people accommodated in emergency shelters as part of their process towards social integration. Within this programme, the Bizitegi organisation provided housing in hostels together with socio-educational support to homeless women. In August 2021, the organisation decided to rent a **hostel where homeless women share the space with tourists**. In the hostel, several activities for socialisation were proposed: a workshop on creative reading and writing; a workshop with a nurse (answering questions about health issues); and the practice of psycho-drama (role-playing to work on conflicts). Leisure activities are also run by volunteers. Other services include legal counselling with a volunteer (especially on how to apply for residence permits/asylum, etc.). This initiative has proven particularly beneficial for homeless women, as it offers them a space to interact with people who see them as their equals, without being identified with their condition.

- **In Italy, Association 21 Luglio launched a programme to reduce food deprivation among Roma children aged 0-3.** At the beginning of the pandemic, the association started a monitoring activity that it carried out through phone interviews to assess the impact of the lockdown on the Roma people living in the five mono-ethnic informal encampments in the City of Rome. The results of this monitoring activity showed that the Roma people were neglected by the public authorities and their living conditions further declined during the state of emergency. The association particularly focused on the problem of food deprivation among children aged 0-3 and implemented a strategy to help families. The strategy relied on fundraising and the work of volunteers.

1.6 Approaching the Crisis as a Continuum: Learning from an Inclusive Feminist Crisis Response

As a way of harvesting our collective insights from the RESISTIRÉ research, we 1) propose the concept of '**crisis as a continuum**' as an essential framework for crisis prevention, response, recovery, and monitoring, and 2) suggest that public authorities at all levels, including the European Union, should support and learn from an **inclusive feminist crisis response** to prevent and better manage future crises. These recommendations are based on the three cycles of RESISTIRÉ research and supported by 14 factsheets that aim to provide a conceptual framework for approaching future crises.

Recommendations for Policymakers

An inclusive and effective approach to future crises requires a fundamental shift in existing practices and a reprioritisation based on a holistic approach to **crisis as a continuum**, which is essential for identifying and addressing the complex and interrelated challenges that arise before, during, and after a crisis, in different places and for different communities and individuals.

Based on the three cycles of RESISTIRÉ research, which are presented in 22 RESISTIRÉ Factsheets (FS), we call on governing bodies at all levels to:

- 1) approach a **crisis as a continuum** and design all processes of crisis prevention, response, recovery, and monitoring on the basis of an understanding of the interconnectedness of the different sites of the crisis (home, workplace, schools, hospitals, public spaces, etc.) and the different moments of the crisis (before, during, after).
- 2) support and learn from an **inclusive feminist crisis response** to prevent and better manage future crises and to co-design and implement **gender+ inclusive**:
 - a. **crisis management plans** in collaboration with diverse groups of CSOs (RESISTIRÉ FS Nos. 8 & 9);

- b. **crisis response policies** that recognise, empower, and fund feminist organisations and other CSOs working with vulnerable communities as key actors in a crisis response (RESISTIRÉ FS Nos. 1, 2, 4, 6a, 6b, 8, 9 & 22);
- c. **recovery plans** and to do so by closely engaging with feminist organisations and other CSOs (RESISTIRÉ FS Nos. 12 & 13);
- d. **monitoring and evaluation systems** that take into account the wide range of experiences and needs of diverse groups, starting with the collection of intersectional data, which is largely missing from national and EU-level data systems (RESISTIRÉ FS No. 21).

Key Insights from the RESISTIRÉ Research

Crises and disasters have a disproportionately negative effect on vulnerable groups. When crises take place in the context of structural inequalities, they escalate into social disasters. In the case of gender+ inequalities, the three cycles of RESISTIRÉ research has shown that the COVID-19 pandemic crisis has had a devastating impact on women and the LGBTQI+, wiping out progress in intersectional gender mainstreaming (RESISTIRÉ FS Nos. 1 and 2), increasing gender-based violence in general (RESISTIRÉ FS Nos. 6a, 6b, and 9) and digital violence in particular (RESISTIRÉ FS No. 10), exacerbating the gender care gaps (RESISTIRÉ FS No. 5), particularly as a result of teleworking (RESISTIRÉ FS Nos. 5 and 7) and distance education (RESISTIRÉ FS No. 11), and deepening the gender inequalities in the healthcare sector (RESISTIRÉ FS No. 3).

The pandemic also highlighted the urgent need to develop comprehensive, inclusive, multi-actor crisis management and recovery plans (RESISTIRÉ FS Nos. 8, 12, and 13). The lack or inefficiency of European-level, national, and municipal 'crisis management plans' has been a major obstacle to just intervention and recovery. The street-level bureaucrats and other experts interviewed by RESISTIRÉ researchers reported on the challenges of addressing the complex issues raised by the pandemic in the absence of (effective) crisis management plans and other measures to meet diverse needs and urgencies (Sandström et al., 2023).

RESISTIRÉ also discovered that in many countries crisis management plans were not inclusive enough to prevent specific rights-violations and meet needs based on gender, sexuality, race, ethnicity, citizenship status, age, disability, and class. Thus, subsequent recovery policies fell short of adequately addressing gender+ inequalities and incorporating intersectional and participatory approaches to recovery (RESISTIRÉ FS Nos. 12 and 13).

Building on Cynthia Cockburn's (2004) concept of *violence as a continuum*, we propose approaching a **crisis as a continuum**, where the emphasis is placed on the interconnectedness of the different sites of the crisis (the home, workplace, schools, hospitals, public spaces, etc.) and different moments of the crisis (before, during, after). The most overt expression of a catastrophic event may occur within a limited timeframe

or at a particular site, but its impact is not time- or site-bound. Moreover, a gender+ intersectional perspective suggests that we live in a world of interconnected, multiple crises: gender-based violence, poverty, racism, state violence, climate crisis, and other forms of slow violence (Nixon, 2011) and slow disaster (Knowles, 2020). RESISTIRÉ research suggests that a crisis is best approached as a continuum, so there is a need to prepare *before* the crisis (e.g. through inclusive crisis management plans and preventive measures), to respond effectively *during* the peak of the crisis, and to attend to the *afterlife* of the crisis (e.g. through inclusive recovery plans and monitoring systems). In the context of the pandemic, CSOs emerged as crucial actors in crisis management and mitigation, who responded more quickly than government authorities, filled the gaps left by governments, provided support and resources to those most in need, and catered to the distinct needs of women, people of colour, the LGBTQI+, older people, and other vulnerable groups, thereby leading to more comprehensive and equitable solutions.

RESISTIRÉ's findings on better stories of the crisis response particularly highlight the accumulated experience, wisdom, and practices of inclusive feminist politics with regards to crisis preparation, management, response, and recovery processes. Feminist and LGBTQI+ organisations, especially those that adopt an intersectional perspective, have played a key role in mitigating the gendered impacts of the pandemic crisis, as well as of the recent earthquake disaster in Turkey, for the most vulnerable communities. The experts interviewed by RESISTIRÉ researchers underscored how an intersectional feminist approach can bring unique perspectives and insights to crisis response efforts. They further argued that while governments and large organisations are struggling to adapt to the changing world, feminist initiatives and CSOs have proven to be more adaptable and responsive in times of crisis. It has also been noted that the capacity for adaptability and for understanding change is a significant advantage that these organisations possess and that make them better equipped to respond to emergencies. The networks, contacts, and trust that CSOs have already built in marginalised communities play a key role in an effective response that takes into account the experiences on the ground.

Collaboration between civil society organisations, initiatives, communities, and government officials is vital to address challenges and generate innovative solutions during a crisis (Cibin et al., 2023). This argument is substantiated by the various examples of experiences being shared through the exchange of information and best practices and the development of continuous dialogue with stakeholders. Similarly, some respondents emphasised the importance of joint planning with CSOs and prioritising various crisis scenarios, while other respondents highlighted the significance of extensive cooperation between local and national institutions (Sandström et al., 2023). Experts have underscored how necessary it is to invest in these collaborations in between crisis outbreaks in order to make service-providing structures more resilient and adaptive when they are most needed (Harroche et al., 2023).

The following are some key lessons to be drawn from the feminist and LGBTQI+ organisations that have developed effective civic responses:

- Multi-actor, collective, and participatory ways of organising and decision-making;
- Using an intersectional lens to expand the organisations' reach and to refine their services to address different needs;
- Making invisible forms of gendered inequality and discrimination visible;
- Investing in community-building both prior to, during, and in the aftermath of the crisis;
- Creating intersectional alliances and communities around the horizontal framework of rights-based 'solidarity' through mutual learning and transformation, rather than by means of top-down, hierarchical frameworks of 'help' or 'charity';
- Building collaborations and networks with all stakeholders in crisis management, including public authorities;
- Monitoring the unequal effects of the crisis in its aftermath.

In short, we argue that as Europe and the world continue to face other crises and disasters, it has become all the more imperative to design policies that approach a *crisis as a continuum* (Cockburn, 2004) and to develop well-integrated mechanisms for inclusive crisis prevention, response, recovery, and monitoring in order to prevent crises from having catastrophic consequences for rights and freedoms and in order to be better prepared for future crises.

1.7 More Intersectional Data

The RESISTIRÉ project examines inequalities using a gender+ approach, which includes the application of a gender perspective in the quantitative and qualitative analyses of other socioeconomic differences. The European datasets that were used over the course of three research cycles of the project provided an opportunity to explore relevant indicators and the unequal experience of different groups during the pandemic. While our data analysis was able to identify and highlight some existing and worsening inequalities, it was often challenging to undertake an intersectional, gender+ approach because of a lack of more accurately representative European-level data.

Intersectional analysis presents a unique opportunity for researchers and institutions to understand how the social and demographic attributes of an individual affect their wellbeing. Moreover, it can be a powerful tool for understanding the underlying structural inequalities that maintain and propagate social inequalities. While these have been amply described in the literature as central to understanding inequalities, they are rarely quantified. However, better and more accurate modelling methodologies have allowed researchers to obtain a more precise understanding of these determinants of wellbeing and should be a catalyst for expanding and improving the data that large-scale surveys collect and make available for researchers to conduct further investigations.

Recommendations

Develop a common European framework for the collection of sociodemographic data

European-level surveys should all include similar sociodemographic variables so that researchers can analyse data more granularly. European institutions have been reluctant to collect data beyond basic sex and socioeconomic characteristics, arguing that doing so can compromise the privacy of respondents. However, there are examples of data collection that have been successful in collecting such data – and in some cases even more sensitive data – without compromising the privacy of users as detailed in the work published by the [National Academy of Sciences regarding data collection on gender and sexuality](#). European data institutions and surveys should find a common ground and consider the necessary steps to safeguard the rights of interviewees, while also collecting more detailed information about their ethnic background, gender identity, and migration status. These can be key to understanding how discrimination affects the health and wellbeing of the European population, which goes well beyond sex and economic differences.

Systematically collect and report data on sex and gender identity

The collection of gender data is a necessary step forward towards enabling wider and more inclusive representation. However, there is an ongoing debate regarding what methods to use to collect information about sex at birth and about how an individual identifies their gender. Some advocate the use of two questions, one asking about sex registered at birth, and a second about current gender identity. Others recommend the use of a third question on alignment between sex at birth and current gender identity as a measure of cis-status. Some North American large-scale surveys such as the [National Health Interview Survey](#) and the [Canadian population census](#) are good examples of successful investigations of the sex, gender, and sexuality of respondents.

Provide harmonised indicators that can be used by researcher to analyse inequalities

Some European surveys offer a rich set of socioeconomic variables; however, these require complex manipulation and the combination of multiple indicators in order to make them comparable across countries, leaving much room for interpretation and error to researchers. Income data collection with EU-SILC data, for example, is disaggregated into many smaller components, which all have different interpretations according to each country's welfare and taxation systems, making comparisons based on income between individuals at the European level very difficult and prone to error. This type of data should be presented also in a standardised, comparable format, as this would make intersectional analysis much easier and more accessible.

Promote intersectional analysis within official European statistics

Understanding the intersectionality of the factors that affect the health and wellbeing of the population is fundamental for truly designing policies that can address systematic inequalities. As of now, Eurostat does not offer any interpretation of its indicators intersectionally (e.g. by presenting outcomes or indicators using intersectional groups), but doing this would facilitate a better understanding of the cumulative disadvantages experienced by vulnerable groups and would encourage researchers to conduct similar analyses.

Promote, strengthen, and innovate the use of Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC) at a wider European level

Statistical confidentiality and privacy are the fundamental rights of every person living in Europe and rank among the central values of the European Statistics Code of Practice. SDC systems help ensure the data protection of every survey respondent and anonymity in their answers and give data providers control over who has access to sensitive data. They are also an important tool for monitoring how databases are used and the research and development that they contribute to. The European Union has a [Centre of Excellence on Statistical Disclosure Control](#) that plays the fundamental role of constantly updating protocols and ensuring the correct usage of data as well as privacy protection. Researchers should be comfortable with these systems and regularly trained on their importance and usage.

Insights from RESISTIRÉ

Sexism, racism, xenophobia, and gender discrimination affect individuals' everyday lives, mental health, and wellbeing, determining both their access to services and their community engagement. While these systemic inequalities determine socioeconomic and health inequalities, few direct observations based on survey data have been made at the European level to show how different, more complex sociodemographic attributes contribute to inequalities in the experiences of everyday lives. The gender+ approach introduced by RESISTIRÉ aims to highlight the intersections between gender and various socioeconomic attributes in an effort to understand and monitor the inequalities that emerged (or that were worsened) as a result of the public health emergency created by the COVID-19 pandemic.

One of the most important findings that surfaced from an analysis of the project's quantitative data is that there is a lack of surveys that offer data on gender and sexual orientation, discrimination, ethnicity, and immigration status across Europe. Such data are necessary for future research at the European level that can inform the design of evidence-based inclusive policies with the potential to address inequities. Major European datasets such as EU-SILC and LFS collect information on sex (largely reflecting

a biological understanding of sex, as opposed to socially constructed gender), however information about gender identity and sexuality is completely lacking.

[Reluctance](#) to collect these data has been primarily justified by the need to ensure the privacy of respondents and to protect them from any form of discrimination. However, this also risks overlooking the experience of these groups and creating a significant knowledge gap in terms of identifying intersectional inequalities and subsequently developing relevant policy responses.

European analysis of cross-national surveys

Our analysis was able to successfully disaggregate inequalities in experiences of the pandemic by key determinants of health and wellbeing:

In the first cycle (Stovell et al., 2021), the quantitative review primarily looked at the available data and scoped the possibility of analysing outcomes by sex and socioeconomic status, focusing mainly on educational level and income quintiles. We were able to observe some pre-existing inequalities that worsened the situation of some people entering the period of social and economic uncertainty created by the pandemic. While we accounted for sex and socioeconomic status, we were unable to disaggregate observations any further owing to the lack of data on other dimensions such as gender identity, ethnicity, and migration status.

In the second cycle (Stovell et al., 2022) our quantitative analysis focused on understanding better the experiences of groups (young/old people, single parents, LGBTQI+, migrants/refugees) who were deemed more socially vulnerable during the public health emergency, owing to the limited information available about their experiences, the well-known barriers they face in accessing services, and the social discrimination they are exposed to daily. While our analysis was able to look at various indicators for each interest group selected, we did not combine interest groups' attributes (such as migration status and household composition). This is mainly because of our methodological approach, which envisioned a more descriptive report, rather than an intersectional analysis.

In the third research cycle (Harroche et al., 2023), we tried to better achieve our aim of performing a gender+ analysis by comparing the experiences of different intersectional groups, which we created by combining sex and educational level. Compared to our previous reports, this analysis was able to apply this intersectionality across all survey items, exploring and observing the different experiences of each group compared to one reference group across different time periods. However, the analysis did not allow any further disaggregation beyond binary sex and educational level because of a lack of available data on other sociodemographic dimensions (such as migration status) and because of the small sample size when it is disaggregated by any additional indicators (such as age).

Part of the quantitative work package also envisioned collaborations with various European researchers to further explore **national Rapid Assessment Surveys (RAS)** (Harroche et al., 2023), which gave us more intersectional, gender+ insights into the experience of people during the pandemic. Seven collaborations were undertaken, and these resulted in new research activities that incorporated a gender+ perspective by adding or modifying collected indicators to address the research agenda of RESISTIRÉ. Furthermore, additional gender+ analysis was conducted on existing RAS data to provide new insights obtained through an intersectional lens. These observations cannot be considered representative of the wider European population since they mostly focus on national samples. However, they contributed to the development of good methodological practices and enriched the pool of secondary data that can be utilised in the future to examine the impact of COVID-19 from a gender+ perspective.

While the evidence reviewed by the quantitative work package of this project was able to put into the spotlight some aspects of the unequal impact of the pandemic and its restrictive measures in Europe, detailed, large-scale intersectional analysis was not possible beyond some basic sociodemographic factors and sex differences. This was primarily hindered by the fact that data disaggregation at the European level remains largely based on education and sex. Importantly, there seems to be no clear standardisation at the European level, forcing the choice of a dataset to be largely based on the disaggregation available, rather than on the topic of investigation.

Good examples of available disaggregation at the European level

The investigation of the wider determinants of health and wellbeing in society is based first and foremost on directly observing the individuals and communities that might be more at risk of discrimination, a given outcome, or hindered in their everyday lives because of their gender, sex, ethnicity, or income. The European Union has long been committed to monitoring and tackling social inequalities and it uses large-scale multi-country surveys as its prime tool of population observation.

The European Union Income and Living Conditions survey (EU-SILC) is perhaps the most well-known and long-standing of these, and this offers detailed information regarding many aspects of an individual's life, including income, sex at birth, and migration status. These characteristics proved to be useful within the scope of our research - for example, migration status could be observed by combining two questions asked (country of birth and country of residence). While this offers some drawbacks (the interpretation of the migration status of the respondents is left to the researcher), it represents the best measurement available to allow us to differentiate the experience between people born in the EU and those who were not.

Eurofound's 'Living, working and COVID-19' e-survey was the most used source for the quantitative analysis, as it had a good sample population, its datasets are easily

accessible, and they were published quickly after their collection. This is in part because the survey was structured and administered online, making the data collection process much faster and cheaper, especially during the height of the COVID-19 pandemic. It also gave Eurofound the opportunity to continue their data collection despite the movement restrictions imposed by governments, making the survey particularly useful for our purpose. Amongst the most interesting aspects related to this dataset was the gender options it offered, adding a third response ('in another way') for respondents to select other than male or female. This allowed us to observe differences between three gender groups, even if the number of people who chose this gender option was generally low in every wave analysed. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first attempt to add an additional option (beyond the usual binary choice between male and female) to a European survey of this magnitude, offering strong hopes for the future.

Finally, the scope of one of the RAS collaborations is especially promising for future research on gender, sexuality, and sex at the cross-national level. [The TransCare COVID-19 survey](#) was developed by a team of researchers (Andreas Koehler, Timo Nieder and Joz Motmans) in cooperation with local healthcare providers and community members and distributed in 80 countries across Europe. It focused on transgender individuals' access to healthcare during the pandemic. The web-based survey was first developed in German and, in cooperation with 23 community organisations, was translated into 26 other languages, collecting 5,267 responses. This represents a successful example of data collection on gender and sex on a European scale, offering a glimpse of what more representative survey data can look like for future research.

1.8 Transformative Funding: A Pathway for Creative and Effective Crisis Response

The RESISTIRÉ research has demonstrated that civil society organisations (CSOs) played an essential role in responding to and managing the COVID-19 pandemic as a crisis, particularly in terms of addressing the needs of the most vulnerable groups and mitigating intersectional and gendered inequalities. Yet the lack of secure, flexible, and sustainable funding interrupted and in some cases hampered these vital efforts. As Europe and the world face multiple and intersecting crises (health, war, energy, food security, environmental degradation, drought, fires, earthquakes, gender-based violence), it has become all the more imperative to design funding schemes that support CSO resilience and enable rapid and effective civic response to crises. This requires a shift in funding schemes towards participatory, transformative, flexible, long-term, capacity-building funding.

Recommendations

Based on the **RESISTIRÉ** research, we argue that for an inclusive and effective crisis response that incorporates the needs of vulnerable groups, CSOs play a crucial role, and that grant-making organisations can be critical allies in co-creating better stories of crisis

prevention, management, and recovery and in transforming philanthropy towards greater inclusion and equality.

We call on major funders of CSOs, including the European Union, to revise their funding schemes so that CSOs have more capacity to respond to needs on the ground, particularly in times of crises, when mainstream funding schemes become hinderers rather than enablers of rapid and effective responses. More specifically, we invite funders to diversify their **forms of funding**, revise the parameters of **the funding process**, allocate rapidly available **crisis funding**, and re-evaluate the **funding mindset**.

Forms of Funding

- Provide **flexible, multi-year, capacity-building funding** - leaving space for experimentation, creativity, and crisis response;
- Combine **long-term core funding** and short-term project-based funding;
- Support **community-led organisations**; enable special funding for grassroots organisations and initiatives led by members of vulnerable groups (through earmarking and other schemes) to help build community resilience and to mobilise local resources to be deployed in times of crisis;
- Use grants to support community philanthropy and community foundations (that are based on the mobilisation of local resources for local issues) to help **build local resilience** to be deployed during times of crises;
- Allow **regranting** to make it possible for smaller organisations to be supported by larger CSOs and to open pathways of collaboration: It is particularly important for funders that are not part of the rights movements they are funding to consult grassroots actors about where the funding should go or give the funding to movement-led and community-led organisations that can facilitate the allocation of funds in a participatory way (through regranting and other means).

The Funding Process

- Conduct research on the funding needs of CSOs and grassroots civic initiatives and **make funding allocations needs-driven**;
- Put an emphasis on the process, and not exclusively on the outcomes, thereby leaving **time for reflection and iterative processes**;
- Make decision-making processes on funding priorities and allocations inclusive - for example, by developing **participatory funding schemes** that enable CSOs and grassroots organisations and movements to decide on funding priorities and allocations;
- **Simplify reporting processes and reduce bureaucracy**: use the information that is already there (and introduce video-reporting as an option when appropriate).

Crisis Funding

- Redefine funding lines and processes based on an understanding of **perpetual and interconnected multiple crises**: gender-based violence, racism, state violence, climate justice, poverty, and other forms of slow violence (Nixon, 2011) and slow disaster (Knowles, 2020);
- Develop **crisis-specific funding schemes** in consultation with grassroots organisations and initiatives to identify and respond to the funding needs on the ground;
- Make **rapid response / emergency funds** available;
- Introduce flexibility into all funding schemes in order to support creative and effective crisis responses by CSOs.

The Funding Mindset

- Redefine the relationship between funders and grantees as one of '*partnership*' (having a more horizontal partnership and sharing common values enable a rapid and effective response during a crisis);
- Acknowledge, learn from, and support the **multiplicity of resources** that communities and grassroots organisations and movements have, such as skills, knowledge, networks, and activist energy, acknowledging that 'money' (as important as it is) is not the only nor the most important resource for an effective crisis response;
- Do not let issues of trust and accountability get in the way of building equal relationships with grassroots organisations and initiatives, and instead **build long-lasting relationships and collaboration** to maintain mutual trust and accountability;
- Re-evaluate all funding processes and outcomes based on questions of inclusion, intersectionality, and fairness, paying particular attention to the **structural inequalities** that result from histories of colonialism, racism, patriarchy, heteronormativity, and ableism.

Problem Statement and Insights from RESISTIRÉ

A report from the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA) indicated that out of 400 CSOs consulted across the EU, 60% experienced difficulty securing funding in 2020, despite some efforts to improve financing frameworks in several Member States (FRA, 2021). The specific challenges related to the allocation of funds that CSOs reported were: competition with other CSOs for limited funds; limited administrative capacity to apply for funding; a lack of transparency and fairness in funding allocation; and restrictive eligibility criteria. CSOs also highlighted pandemic-related funding issues such as 'the diversion of public funds to other priorities, a decrease in private donations and the inability to organise fundraising events, and a decline in in-kind contributions

such as volunteering' (FRA, 2021, p. 8). Similar to RESISTIRÉ's findings, FRA's research also highlighted the discriminatory and restrictive funding practices that exist in a number of EU countries and that are especially a problem for CSOs focusing on gender equality and LGBTQI+ rights, as well as those working with migrant communities and religious minorities.

RESISTIRÉ's research has demonstrated the essential role that civil society organisations and solidarity initiatives played in managing the pandemic crisis by attending to the multidimensional needs of vulnerable groups, mitigating gendered inequalities, and filling the gaps left by public institutions and social protection measures (Altınay et al., 2022; Cibin et al., 2023; Sandström et al., 2023). Nevertheless, CSOs, which were already suffering from a lack of sustainable funding before the pandemic, had difficulty finding and accessing stable funding opportunities during the pandemic (Cibin et al., 2023). Furthermore, many governments and donors suspended grants and froze funding to CSOs during the pandemic, which made the situation even more difficult for CSOs and forced some of them to put their activities on hold (CIVICUS, 2020). This represented a threat not only to the CSOs' sustainability but also to their ability to continue to serve their communities and fulfil their vital role, especially in crisis situations (CIVICUS, 2020). The situation is even worse for CSOs working on human rights and advocacy than it is for CSOs providing services. For example, organisations engaged in women's and LGBTQI+ rights played a key role in the struggle against GBV during the pandemic, but they often did not receive financial assistance from the government and were typically left out of crisis resilience funding (Altınay et al., 2022).

The CSO representatives consulted for RESISTIRÉ described the allocation of short-term funding through projects as an obstacle to the urgent crisis-specific work that has to be done during a crisis situation and highlighted the need to move away from project-based logic in order to maintain the work of CSOs and their relationships with their beneficiaries (Cibin et al., 2023). Many of the CSO initiatives mapped by RESISTIRÉ as better stories had received financial support, directly or indirectly, from national, regional, or local public authorities, which highlights the significance of these resources in enabling CSOs to navigate the pandemic challenges and to offer effective support to vulnerable groups (Cibin et al., 2023). These public funds were in most cases made available for the purpose of responding specifically to the pandemic. For example, in Iceland, a café aimed at addressing social isolation among people in poverty received funding from a municipal programme specifically created to support pandemic-related activities. Similarly, a Swedish organisation that helps young migrants utilised funds from the Swedish Agency for Youth and Civil Society that targeted at organisations assisting vulnerable populations during the pandemic. In Italy, an organisation focused on youth in education obtained government funds to pay for summer camps and aid families in need. In Spain, a regional government programme financed an initiative that turned a hostel into a shelter for homeless women, while in Prague the municipal government provided full funding for an initiative that converted some hotels into homeless shelters.

The COVID-19 pandemic demonstrated that with adequate funding, CSOs can play a

critical role in reducing inequalities among vulnerable populations and responding to the urgent needs of individuals neglected by the public authorities. Therefore, the emergency response approach of relying on CSOs must be transformed into a more permanent funding solution to ensure their long-term stability (Cibin et al., 2023). Yet, public funding for CSO work during the pandemic was rare and generally temporary.

RESISTIRÉ's research and workshops with CSO representatives suggest that current funding schemes have several shortcomings that limit the possibility of developing creative civic responses to crises:

- Most funding for civil society organisations and initiatives is **short-term and project-based** (which limits capacity-building, long-term and strategic planning, and the flexibility needed for an effective crisis response);
- CSOs operate with a **mentality of 'scarcity'** (of funding) and find themselves in competition with each other (which limits their creativity and ability to take risks);
- Short-term project funding leaves **CSO staff in an insecure and precarious position** (which makes it difficult for them to make long-term plans and to invest in capacity-building and well-being, and limits their ability to respond and respond creatively to crises);
- Funding priorities and funding decisions are typically made in a **top-down decision-making process**;
- Grassroots organisations, initiatives, and movements often **do not participate in the decision-making process** regarding the allocation of funds, even though they are the ones who know the needs and funding priorities on the ground;
- **Hierarchical relationships** between the providers and recipients of grants limit the possibility of meaningful, creative engagement in the funding relationship;
- Significant time and energy are spent on **bureaucratic procedures**, which create additional barriers for grassroots organisations and initiatives and make it difficult to effect the rapid adjustments that are needed, particularly in times of crises with changing situations and needs.

In recent years, an increasing number of funders have moved away from the established hierarchical models of funding, fixated on full oversight and control over the specific uses of the money and the project outcomes, towards new, transformative funding schemes that are more horizontal, participatory, flexible, long-term, and creative. At the same time, there are growing numbers of (particularly feminist) initiatives that seek to outline new principles for participatory, transformative, flexible, long-term, capacity-building funding

Suggested resources for feminist funding principles and toolkits

[Feminist Funding Principles](#)

[Lighting the Way - shake the table](#)

[Resource Mobilization Toolkit](#)

[Transforming philanthropy with feminist principles](#) [Where is the Money for Feminist Organizing?](#)

A Better Story

The Feminist Fund Poland (FemFund) has been providing consistent support to grassroots organising across Poland since 2018. It manages the fund on the basis of an understanding that women, girls, and feminist groups know best what actions are necessary. FemFund Poland's priorities involve supporting groups that resist patriarchy, oppression, and the structures of power and capitalism. This support may take the form of responding to emergencies or promoting self-care and community care. FemFund provides support to a wide range of groups and organisations, such as rural housewives and anarchist collectives, sex educators and abortion providers, female athletes and artists, environmental activists and refugees, mothers before and after childbirth, people with disabilities and the carers of these people, trans people and those non-heteronormative and non-binary people manifesting on the streets, and pensioners and employees fighting for their rights, as these are the groups most commonly discriminated against.

Fem Fund Poland embraces *feminist philanthropy* and practises participatory grant-making, whereby the money they raise is allocated to feminist plans and needs identified by the members of the feminist and LGBTQI+ movement themselves.

Magdalena Pocheć, one of the founders of the Fund, explains the history, grant-making model and principles of the Fund as follows:

'Feminist Fund Poland was started by three activists who emerged from the feminist movement. The Feminist Fund Poland positions itself as part of the feminist and LGBTQI+ movement. There is shared ownership over the fund as individual supporters contribute monthly to make the fund sustainable. Being movement-led and community-led, our grant-making is based on facilitating the process of mobilising resources and of collective decision-making regarding the distribution of the funds. After issuing an open grant call every year, we receive proposals. Then, applicants/activists read each other's proposals, discuss the priorities for allocating the funding, and tell FemFund where the money should go. 75% of the funds are allocated through the participatory grant-making process. The remaining 25% is decided on by the Advisory Board that seeks to identify who or what is still missing among the potential grantees. Through this participatory grant-making model, grant-making becomes an act of solidarity and power shifting. Thanks to this model, activists who are part of the community are also learning from each other and building new networks of solidarity. The transparency of the process also helps trust-building and co-creation.'

The pandemic reaffirmed the importance of unrestricted funding, the role of communities, and transnational solidarity. Thanks to the flexible budget that FemFund

manages, we were able to swiftly and smoothly respond to changing priorities on the ground. FemFund's grantee partners were free to use the funding as they needed. We carried out online sessions to share our experiences and support each other. We could also count on FemFund's international partners and donors that expressed their solidarity by encouraging us to follow our needs and demonstrated full trust in us.'

2. Agenda for Future Research

The aim of the research agenda is to identify knowledge gaps and formulate future research needs to understand/mitigate/address behavioural, social, and economic inequalities produced by the policy responses to COVID-19. The purpose in this last cycle is to identify knowledge gaps for future research agendas to be taken up by research funders.

The findings produced by RESISTIRÉ during the research phase are based on the analysis of various empirical data collected and analysed in different work packages: the mapping of policies/civil society organisation initiatives; official secondary data sources at the international and EU level, as well as RAS at the national level; expert interviews/workshops; and narratives from members of vulnerable groups. In the research agenda, these findings have been synthesised to identify what knowledge is currently missing in order to support further research aimed at improving the development and implementation of COVID-19-induced policies/responses considering their impacts on vulnerable groups and (pre-)existing inequalities.

The research agendas included below have been developed in stages, comparable to the approach followed for the Operational Recommendations described above with a leader and team/contributors appointed for each research agenda theme. Knowledge gaps and related research questions were identified based on the results of WP2, WP3 and WP4, which were then compiled in initial drafts of six research agendas. These first drafts served as input for a consortium workshop, and a process of further development and finalisation after the workshop. There were two main differences in comparison to the Operational Recommendations: the input from the Open Studios was less substantive and the workshop participants were solely consortium members, no external experts were invited.

The workshop among the consortium partners was held in Gothenburg on 23rd March 2023, and was organised by ORU/UGOT as the task leader. Before the workshop, the consortium partners had received access to the six research agenda drafts and, during the workshop and in small groups, they were able to (re)read these documents. After everyone had familiarised themselves with the documents, they reflected on the knowledge gaps/research questions that were already included, as well as any dimensions that might be missing. Afterwards, the results were presented in plenary. Following the workshop, the six research agendas were revised by the leads of each research agenda, collectively reviewed by the partners in the task, and finalised by the task leader. The final drafts were quality reviewed by the consortium.

In the following section, the report provides an overview of the final research agendas for the six areas that were identified. These include health inequalities, inequalities in age and ageing, digitalisation, gender+ inclusive green spaces, civic responses to crisis,

and gender-based violence. For each domain, findings from the project are provided, as well as knowledge gaps identified based on the empirical data collection and analysis, and potential research questions.

It is important to note that RESISTIRÉ's previous cycles of activities produced research agendas, with their own distinct knowledge gaps and research questions, on some of the same general topics that are considered in this cycle's research agenda (i.e., gender-based violence). These additional research agenda topics are not repeated in detail here but can be consulted in the research agenda of the first cycle (Živković et al., 2022), the report on solutions for the first cycle (Živković et al., 2021), the research agenda of the second cycle (Sandström & Strid, 2022), and the report on solutions for the second cycle (Kerremans & Denis, 2022).

2.1 Research Agenda on Health Inequalities

Identified as a public health emergency at the beginning of 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic has hit globally not only in terms of infections and deaths, but also in terms of various health-related aspects that both directly and indirectly were affected. While a large number of studies - including RESISTIRÉ - has already shown the short-term/immediate effects of COVID-19 on mental health, access to healthcare and particularly the impacts of the pandemic on health and healthcare access of vulnerable groups, more research is needed to understand the long-term impacts on health and health inequalities. Building on the Research Agenda on Human Rights and Health of cycle 1 (Živković et al., 2022), which was more focused on understanding the immediate consequences of the pandemic for healthcare access, healthcare workers and vaccination inequalities, the current Research Agenda identifies five key themes related to long-term impact of COVID-19 on health, which are presented in more details below.

Long-term and intersectional effects on mental health

As shown from the findings of RESISTIRÉ and broad research, mental health was severely affected, with some social groups suffering more compared to others (Camara et al., 2023; OECD, 2021; Stovell et al., 2022). Several RAS mapped by RESISTIRÉ have highlighted that mental health has deteriorated, especially among young people and people in precarious working conditions, because of intersecting problems such as economic instability, isolation, and closure of schools (Stovell et al., 2022).

The pandemic has uncovered well-established gaps and a worldwide underinvestment in mental health prevention and care (The Lancet Public Health, 2022). As highlighted in the narrative interviews collected by RESISTIRÉ, the fact that the pandemic spotlighted mental health, and the awareness that others were suffering too, made it easier for many to address their mental health issues, thus becoming a better story of solidarity. Some individuals from marginalised groups reported to have sought professional help, others practiced different forms of self-care that they hoped to sustain in the long-term. What

should be explored further is whether the negative impact of the pandemic on mental health will last for how long, and among which groups these consequences will be more long-lasting.

A closely related topic investigated in RESISTIRÉ analysis is resilience, which refers to the capacity to maintain or recover mental health, despite experiencing adversity (Herrman et al., 2011; see Sandström et al., 2022). Resilient individuals play a fundamental role in resilient communities and societies, and the pandemic has made clear how important is to develop resilience in the society to prepare individuals to face future challenges (Joossens et al., 2022). The findings from the EU quantitative analysis reveal that lower levels of resilience are prevalent among some Europeans sub-groups three years after the COVID-19 outbreak, such as among lower educated women. However, the focus on individual resilience risks over-emphasising individuals' capacities and self-reliance (i.e., the micro level), and in effect, under-emphasising the responsibility of authorities and the role of structures (i.e., the macro level). To build and strengthen the resilience of a population, it is necessary to develop a system of infrastructure and collective resources that is resilient to external adversities. National level strategies such as building trust, strengthen solidarity, fostering resilience leadership, or providing mental health services on time to people in need are some possible ways to foster resilience (Zhang et al., 2022). Researchers are urged to explore how a resilient system can be built and maintained in context of long-lasting and overlapping crises, such as in the current period.

Research questions:

- *What are the long-term impacts of the pandemic (and overlapping crises) on mental health? How has the pandemic affected gender+ inequalities in mental health? Lessons can be drawn from, and research build on, previous crises.*
- *What are the effective policies/initiatives to address mental health on the long-term among vulnerable populations? Lessons can be drawn from, and research build on, previous crises.*
- *What have we learned from the pandemic in relation to addressing mental health status during a crisis? What responses work, and which do not work? What changes from the pandemic should be kept?*
- *What are the resources needed to increase resilience - especially among vulnerable groups - and how can resilience be built into the structures/authorities to support individuals?*

Unequal access to sexual and reproductive health

The pandemic stressed the capacity of hospitals and healthcare systems, forcing many countries - especially in the first year of the crisis - to reduce or postpone non-essential medical care (OECD, 2021). Unmet healthcare needs became particularly evident in some specific areas of health and for some individuals, which were the focus of RESISTIRÉ throughout the different cycles (Stovell et al., 2021; Stovell et al., 2022;

Harroche et al., 2023).

A group experiencing obstacles and inequalities in access to healthcare during the pandemic was that of transgender people, whose treatments were largely interrupted due to the priority given to COVID-19-related treatments. The cross-sectional international study TransCareCovid-19 survey investigated the effects of the pandemic on healthcare for transgender individuals (Koehler et al., 2021) and the collaboration of the authors of the survey with the RESISTIRÉ team contributed to bring intersectional insights to these topic (Harroche et al., 2023). More than half of the respondents of the survey indicated they experienced restrictions in at least one type of healthcare (among access to hormones, hair removal treatment, surgery, aftercare and mental healthcare). More counselling support, improved medical knowledge about trans-specific issues among healthcare providers, and a lower threshold for service accessibility were recurrent themes among the answers given to the question of what services respondents wanted to see from the (trans) health providers in the current pandemic situation. These findings are relevant starting points indicating the specific healthcare needs of a group of the population, and how the system should take these needs into account to address potential inequalities in access to healthcare.

Another area of healthcare that was strongly affected by the pandemic was that of sexual and reproductive health, which in many countries was temporarily 'put aside' to leave more space for COVID-19-related care. An example was reported by an Italian street-level bureaucrat member of the centres for family advice, interviewed in the context of RESISTIRÉ qualitative analysis (Sandström et al., 2023). During the peak of COVID-19, the services offered - ranging from gynaecological counselling to cancer screening - were completely suspended, significantly affecting the health of specific groups for which these services were essential, such as migrant women. The suspension of healthcare service, even if only temporary, will likely generate consequences also in the long term, for example with the creation of long waiting lists once the services were restored (Cibin et al., 2023), especially for vulnerable groups such as women with a lower socioeconomic status and for the LGBTQ+ communities. Understanding the impact of decreased access to healthcare, and how healthcare services are considered or defined essential, is a task for future research.

There are also examples of civil societies initiatives mapped by RESISTIRÉ addressing specifically the issue of access to sexual and reproductive healthcare for marginalised groups, which can be considered as better stories. For example, in Hungary a gynaecological clinic for homeless (often traumatised) women was installed; in Denmark, treatment for sex workers with drug addictions were offered directly in the places they frequent and not only in clinics (which are often considered unsafe and uncomfortable); organisations in Romania and Croatia worked to offer support to women who had problems with obtaining access to abortion-related services, services that were often deemed to be non-essential as a result of restrictions on mobility and hospital access. Going beyond sexual health, an initiative (in Belgium) focused on bringing healthcare and information to marginalised places: here, community health

workers conduct outreach activities in deprived neighbourhoods of which they themselves are part. Future research should further investigate these initiatives, which could be beneficial not only for some specific vulnerable groups, but they can also be extended to different groups with particular needs.

In this context, the effects of the pandemic on the postponement or suspension of specific treatments should be investigated in a comparative perspective, as it is likely that not all the countries applied the same rules for prioritisation of healthcare services. The TransCareCovid-19 survey, for example, was carried out in 80 countries, however the sample size for each country did not allow to comparatively study the effects of COVID-19 national policies on access to transgender healthcare. More research is thus needed to understand how different contexts might affect differently access to healthcare, and the right to sexual and reproductive health.

Research questions:

- *What are the short and long terms impacts of decreased access to sexual and reproductive care during the crisis? What are the effects on vulnerable groups?*
- *How can the continuation of essential sexual and reproductive services during a crisis be ensured? Are special measures needed to ensure continuation of healthcare services among vulnerable groups?*
- *Which countries, or welfare regimes have produced better outcomes in terms of healthcare access, and for which groups? Which countries, or welfare regimes have increased inequalities in terms of healthcare access, and for which groups?*
- *How can the sustainability of civil society initiatives carried out during the pandemic to address healthcare needs of vulnerable groups be ensured (especially in case of future health crises)? How can these better stories be made more widespread?*

Access to preventive resources for physical and mental health

The pandemic created different types of health-related needs, directly related to reducing the risks of getting infected or spread the virus, or related to individuals' wellbeing more in general. Preventive resources include not only resources related to COVID-19 prevention (e.g., masks and gels), but other resources necessary for individuals' health, such as green spaces for physical activity, healthy foods, and/or psychological support. RESISTIRÉ research, in line with previous research, has highlighted inequalities in access to these resources, where social class (accentuated by the intersection with other inequality grounds, such as gender or ethnicity) is a primary source of differentiated access.

For example, studies have shown that socially deprived neighbourhoods are generally less green, or are more distant from urban green space (Hoffmann et al., 2017; Schüle et al., 2019). The movement restrictions imposed by the COVID-19 policies have removed the possibility for residents of areas without urban green spaces to access

better quality and clean air environments, with severe impacts on physical and mental health. Despite differences in the policies implemented by countries, the impossibility of staying in close contact with nature and evading the city was reported by the people interviewed by RESISTIRÉ. A similar pattern can be identified regarding nutritional habits. National studies during the pandemic have shown that the decrease in fruit and vegetable consumption was more pronounced for the most deprived compared to the least deprived groups, and for women compared to men (Braithwaite et al., 2022). Food banks or other initiatives at the local level reported by interviewed people within RESISTIRÉ (e.g., providing hygiene kits and food packages) were helpful for those in need. Regarding psychological support, while some experiences reported in the RESISTIRÉ narratives talked about this type of support offered to frontline workers, this was not tailored to specific needs of this heterogeneous work category; in other cases, psychological support services were interrupted, with detrimental consequences for people's mental health (especially the most vulnerable ones). All these examples show how the pandemic has acted on existing health inequalities, reinforcing them and in some cases even worsening them.

Research questions:

- *What are the short and long terms impacts of reduced access to preventive services during the crisis on health and well-being for the population? Which services, with reduced access, had the most impact? Which groups of the population were most effected by the reduced services?*
- *What measures are needed to ensure fair access to adequate prevention measures? How can these measures be made affordable for those who need them?*
- *What was the impact of solidarity and local civil society organisations (CSOs) in making preventive resources available for the groups in need during the crisis? What lessons can be drawn for future crisis?*

Institutional support and interconnections between civil societies and professionals

For some aspects, the bureaucracy and resistance to change of public institutions were hindering factors for the creation of quick response to the crisis. Where institutions could not be successful in addressing specific needs of (especially vulnerable) population, CSOs were able to activate themselves and experiment innovative practices that would not usually be allowed. This was the case, for example, of Denmark (the above-mentioned initiative). The policy mapping highlighted, however, cases in which policies helped to improve the situations of the vulnerable people; for example, the municipality of the capital and the district in Hungary started various initiatives to mitigate the effect of the crisis, such as organising food distribution, allocating resources, offering support to older people and distributing masks; in Italy, strong efforts at the governance level were made to create an inclusive communication campaign about vaccination that could include also less integrated citizens such as migrants; in Czech Republic, an association

of medical students (*Medici na ulici*) supported homeless people directly by offering basic medical treatments in mobile units or directly on the field.

These examples of coordination between high-level institutions (being municipalities, or governments) and the bottom-up initiatives should be further investigated, to analyse their short- and long-term effects on the health of their target groups.

Research questions:

- *What lessons can be learned from the crisis in integrating quick and innovative responses in already existing institutional structures?*
- *What lessons can be learned from the crisis to strengthen the relation between healthcare professionals and CSOs?*
- *How to sustain successful measures taken during the crisis such mobile health units? How can these initiatives be supported by institutions and how can they support institutional services?*

Digital literacy and health

The suspension of face-to-face health service resulted, in many countries, in a provision of alternative online e-services. Accessing and understanding these services require both digital means and literacy that might not be available to all population groups, as evidenced from RESISTIRÉ research of the three cycles, and some research questions on this topic were already proposed in the Research Agenda of cycle 1 (Živković et al., 2022). Nevertheless, the switch to digital services proved to be very useful during the crisis, when otherwise no alternatives could be accessed (see research questions in the Digitalisation section). The use of digital services may be impacted by other factors than just having the tools and skills to access the services: while some population groups might be enthusiastic about the use of digital tools, others might be reluctant to use them, even if they have all the resources necessary to access and understand them. Some studies on the use of video consultation for primary care, for example, show that patients are generally satisfied, compared to online or face-to-face consultations, when video consultations help them saving time (Donaghy et al., 2019) and they were the only resource available during the pandemic, thus “better than nothing” (Hvidt et al., 2022). Yet, face-to-face consultations seem to be preferred when related to very personal or serious issues (Donaghy et al., 2019). Few studies have explored this topic, and these are mainly focused on practitioners’ attitudes or outside the European context. Both quantitative and qualitative research should address this gap, to provide policymakers with a clearer picture of the extent to which digital health services have been used by different social groups, and whether they could be further developed to ease the burden of healthcare.

Research questions:

- *How has digitalisation impacted access to care during the crisis? Does this impact differ by groups users or by the type of service?*

- *How are digital (health) services perceived by potential users? Beyond tools and skills, which groups are more reluctant to use these tools, and why?*

2.2 Research Agenda on Inequalities in Age and Ageing

In all three cycles of RESISTIRÉ, inequalities related to older persons have been prominent. During the pandemic, medical reports quickly established that the virus hits the older population the hardest, although they were not more likely to contract the virus than other age groups. Studies show how this vulnerability often was regarded as a fate or the “natural order of things” (Beaulieu et al, 2020)). Yet, studies have established how prejudices, institutional bias and societal discrimination against older persons interact and create inequalities and negative effects beyond the pure medical aspects of the virus. While ageism is not a new feature in society, the pandemic both exposed, and increased, age-related inequalities, showing how vulnerabilities relating to age - and affecting older persons - are both a condition and set of processes (Zarowsky et al., 2013). These vulnerabilities are co-constructed by other structural barriers, such as racism, misogyny, and ableism (Henderson & Sawchuk, 2022; Katz et al., 2019). Ageism and age discrimination in society remain unrecognised and unchallenged (Equinet, 2020), even though discrimination based on age is the most widespread form of discrimination in Europe (FRA, 2018). Based on the findings of RESISTIRÉ, this Research Agenda identifies three key areas where more research is needed.

The role of older persons in crises policymaking and crisis responses

Both in research and activism, the active role of older persons during crises has been highlighted as undervalued and made invisible, especially the active role of older women. There is a discourse which upholds beliefs about the shortcomings of older persons, rather than highlighting their contributions, strengths, or resilience (Henderson and Sawchuk, 2022; McLaren et al., 2020). While the impact of ageism was raised early on in the pandemic, warning of a “parallel outbreak of ageism”, it was not addressed sufficiently in pandemic policymaking (Ayalon et al., 2020: 49). Even when pandemic measures were reported to address the specific needs of older persons, there were many accounts of the lack of attention to gender in “mainstream” policies, such as the lack of specific measures to address the increasing violence towards older women. The RESISTIRÉ analysis of pandemic policy measures shows that in most cases little attention was paid to ensuring the (continued) inclusion of older people in social and civic life (Cibin et al., 2021, 2022), and the narrative analysis show the effects of this omission (Axelsson et al., 2021; Sandström et al., 2022, 2023). Furthermore, the RESISTIRÉ findings suggest that for many older people, the pandemic is ‘not over’. The levels of inclusion and social activities enjoyed by some senior citizens have not returned to the pre-pandemic levels. Due to the long-term impact of such prolonged social isolation, this needs further scrutiny and research. Furthermore, the mapping of the National Recovery and Resilience Plans (and equivalent recovery policies) show that even if age is frequently mentioned, it was in the form of generic statements underlining how the

pandemic particularly affected older persons, without any specificities related to sex or gender of the seemingly homogenous group 'older persons' (Cibin et al., 2022).

Future research in this field should therefore focus on further identifying gaps in how age and ageism are integrated (or not) into crises policymaking and crises responses in order to attain better knowledge about how integration can be strengthened on a European, national and local level and across different actors and organisations.

Research questions:

- *In what ways have the needs, experiences and interests of older persons been integrated into crises management pre, during and post-pandemic and why?*
- *How have the negative effects on older persons wellbeing from the pandemic been considered in recovery strategies?*
- *What (are the main factors that) impact on the inclusion of older persons in crises policymaking e.g., policy consultation and representation?*
- *How can older persons' active participation in crises policymaking and crises responses be strengthened, and made visible?*

The impact of the pandemic on older persons from a gender+ perspective

Loneliness, isolation, and mental illnesses of older persons, especially relating to older women, were highlighted in RESISTIRÉ quantitative and qualitative research (Axelsson et al., 2021; Sandström et al., 2022; Sandström et al., 2023; Stovell et al., 2021). Overall, however, the RESISTIRÉ mapped national RAS only focused on older people's experiences to a small extent, and when these experiences were included, the number of older respondents was small. There were also small numbers of older respondents in some in some EU COVID-19 surveys (Stovell et al., 2022). The mapped RAS that did include a focus on age, and did not reveal that social distancing, fears of contracting COVID-19, and disruption of normal routines had negative impacts, with loneliness and anxiety found to be a particular problem. One example is how social isolation has consequences for life expectancy; isolation was found to increase the risks of cardiovascular, cognitive, psychological, and hormonal conditions. Other examples are how the loss of care responsibilities, e.g., for grandchildren, due to social distancing restrictions had negative impacts on mental health and where older women were at a higher risk of experiencing anxiety than older men. When looking at the intersection of age and pre-existing intellectual disability, women respondents experienced more stress and anxiety than men. Other examples were how higher risk of anxiety was linked to women being more likely to live alone, have lower income levels, and experience chronic illness, making them more dependent on others and therefore at a greater risk of abuse (Stovell et al., 2022). The RESISTIRÉ results also show a worsening economic situation for older persons, especially for those who do not have work and do not receive enough pensions. The intersection of gender (the fact that older women are more at risk of poverty than men were a common theme), nationality, class and age was particularly

salient as many care workers are older migrant women whose working conditions, and financial situation, are highly precarious (Axelsson et al., 2021; Sandström et al., 2022). Earlier research has pointed to the need to adopt a lifecycle or life span perspective to understand the diverse needs and experiences of older persons (Diehl & Wahl, 2020). Older persons are a largely heterogeneous group that differ in life experiences, cultural backgrounds, health, and the process of aging itself is highly diverse and contextually embedded (ibid.; Ayalon et al., 2020). In general, RESISTIRÉ shows that there was limited consideration of gender in data collection such as in surveys addressing older people across EU, with only a third considering the differences between older women and men. This could point to a significant gap in the data and may indicate assumptions about the homogeneity of older people's experiences (Stovell et al., 2022).

Future research in this field should therefore focus on creating a better understanding of the short term and long-term effects on older persons wellbeing beyond mere health/medical aspects. Special attention is needed to uncover intersectional aspects and in applying a lifecycle approach to better understand which groups of older persons are more at risk in crises situations and why.

Research questions:

- *In what ways have the physical and psychological wellbeing of older persons been affected by the pandemic and why?*
- *How have intersecting strands of inequalities affected the wellbeing of different groups of older people and why?*
- *How will long-term cognitive health of older adults be affected by the pandemic and prolonged isolation? What will be the impact on global cognitive impairment prevalence?*

Ageism and discrimination of older persons in times of crises

Ageism and age discrimination in society remains unrecognised and unchallenged (Equinet, 2020), even though age is one of the most widespread forms of discrimination across Europe, including the right to life (FRA, 2018). Other reports included the risk of neglect, violence, and financial exploitation of older persons; stereotyping, prejudice or discrimination against individuals or groups based on their age; stigmatisation and hate speech; threats to the social and economic well-being; and the situation of specific groups of older people. Many of which has resulted from the pandemic restrictions imposed rather than from the virus itself. The RESISTIRÉ mapping of pandemic policies has revealed how the restrictions imposed on older persons have affected their freedom of movement, including restrictions on when and where they could shop, not being able to receive visitors in nursing homes, and bans to use public transport for older person (Cibin et al., 2021). In the narratives, older people often expressed that the policy meant to protect them often left them feeling vulnerable and excluded (Axelsson et al., 2021). The results have furthermore highlighted a digital age gap, with negative consequences

for the possibilities to bridge the restrictions imposed in receiving information, access to health care and to communicate and stay in contact with friends and relatives (Cibin et al., 2021).

Future research in this field should therefore focus on creating a better understanding of ageism in times of crises and the invisibility and lack of attention to ageism and age discrimination in crises policymaking and crises responses. Research needs to especially focus on the lack of intersectional approaches and the perceived homogeneity of older persons.

Research questions:

- *How can discrimination towards older persons be prevented in crises?*
- *What impact on, and sustains, effective policies to expose and remedy age-based discrimination in crises and beyond and why?*
- *How can intersectional policy analysis that addresses ageism and age-based discrimination be strengthened?*

2.3 Research Agenda on Digitalisation

Digitalisation, referred to as the development and deployment of digital technologies and processes, has taken on a new dimension since the COVID-19 pandemic. When faced with social distancing and the closure of workplaces, schools and other public and private institutions going digital was often the only solution. Many activities carried out remotely included teleworking, online schooling, and access to public services during the crisis. However, while the practices initiated during the various lockdowns accelerated digitalisation, the increased reliance on digital devices, especially for essential services such as education and healthcare, had detrimental effects on many vulnerable groups and increased the digital divide (see RESISTIRÉ Agenda for Future Research - cycle 2 (Sandström & Strid, 2022)). Given the ambivalent nature of this phenomenon and its growing role in all aspects of life, further research must be conducted. Building on the findings from the previous cycles of RESISTIRÉ, we will present research gaps related to digitalisation that have been identified during the third cycle. Firstly, we will address the need to tackle this phenomenon through an intersectional lens. Secondly, we will highlight the implications for public policy and human rights. Finally, we will consider the role of CSOs and the necessity to research these issues at an organisational level.

Digitalisation through an intersectional lens

The third cycle RAS analysis (Harroche et al., 2023) highlighted the worsening of digital inequalities due to the pandemic, reinforcing the findings from international literature (Beaunoyer et al., 2020). Accessing digital resources and knowing how to use them was a key issue during lockdowns, impeding a high proportion of senior citizens' access to

information, services, and social contacts, and working-class children and students' ability to attend classes. While many authors acknowledge that digital inequalities are embedded in other inequalities (Robinson et al., 2015), few studies have looked at this issue regarding the COVID-19 crisis considering multiple, intersecting inequality grounds. The rare studies that do so highlight new kinds of phenomena rising within vulnerable groups. For instance, concurring with findings presented in the RESISTIRÉ factsheet on safe digital spaces, a survey carried out in Ireland on LGBTI+ lockdown experiences showed that Black and South Asian LGBTQ+ people were more than twice as likely to experience violence or abuse, including online violence, during lockdowns compared to white LGBTQ+ people (survey conducted by Belong to LGBTQ+ Youth Ireland). Thus, there is an urgent need for intersectional approaches to better understand digitalisation and for data on ethnicity, race, gender identity, sexual orientation, religion, citizenship status etc. to be more systematically collected and analysed in order to document effects and help mitigate them.

Research questions:

- *How can digitalisation and the digital divide be researched through an intersectional lens?*
- *What conditions are necessary for digitalisation to prevent exacerbating intersectional inequalities for vulnerable groups?*

Public services

The findings from Cycle 3 highlight the advantages and disadvantages of digitalisation in the provision of public services. The shift to online/phone services was crucial in maintaining education, welfare and healthcare services during the pandemic while enabling greater access to municipal services for individuals living on the outskirts of cities. In specific situations, such as gender-based violence, digital tools have proven useful in maintaining contact with victims. From the perspective of street-level bureaucrats, digitalisation has enabled them to save time on certain services and organise work and resources more efficiently. However, those who depended the most on state services and benefits (e.g., refugees, homeless people, those from more disadvantaged socio-economic backgrounds) were negatively affected by the rapid switch from face-to-face to online services. More specifically, multiple RAS showed that language inequalities fed into digital inequalities and acted as barriers to accessing public services and benefits when they were made available solely through online platforms.

Research questions:

- *How have public services changed as a result of the impact of digitalisation? What differences can we see across countries and what can we learn from them?*
- *How can we ensure that better stories and inclusive digitalisation strategies can be maintained in the long term?*
- *Which factors/conditions can foster an inclusive digital transformation of public*

services?

- *How can we assess the impact of new technologies introduced as part of digitalisation in public services?*
- *What institutional strategies were introduced to shift towards the digital provision of public services? To what extent were such strategies underpinned by an inclusive review of services and ongoing monitoring?*
- *How can we ensure that the perceived positive effects of digitalisation can be maintained in the long term?*

Digital rights

According to international literature, digitalisation can lead to new forms of discrimination and has the potential to alter people's rights. RESISTIRÉ's third cycle results have shown differential impacts of digitalisation in terms of access to public services, access to equipment and technology and digital literacy skills (digital divide) with implications regarding human rights that have the potential to create "second-class citizens". Thus, there is a need to better understand digital rights including privacy, freedom of expression, access to information, IP (Internet Protocol), network neutrality, digital access, and cybersecurity. The evolution of government actions through digitalisation needs to be further researched especially given the preponderant role of AI and algorithms that are now emerging.

It is crucial to consider the implications of digital transformation on access to information, which is a fundamental human right. Further research is needed to ensure that this right is guaranteed in the context of digitalisation. With the widespread adoption of digital media and the growing reliance on social media for news consumption, coupled with the proliferation of 'fake news', particularly during times of crisis, it is necessary to further research how to ensure the development of digital critical thinking skills for all. The design process of digital innovation has been identified as a critical step in safeguarding digital rights. Initiatives such as "Universal design" and "Design justice" have emerged to mitigate the detrimental aspects of digitalisation and promote inclusivity through active participation and engagement of users in the design process to ensure that digital technologies, products, and services are accessible and user friendly for all. Attention to design is also underlined by the European Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles.

Research questions:

- *What are the implications of the digital divide regarding human rights and democracy?*
- *Can digital rights be guaranteed? If so, how?*
- *How can access to information and media literacy be ensured and developed in the context of digitalisation?*

CSO digitalisation

Digitalisation has been described as improving work processes and the internal sharing of information within organisations, especially civil society organisations (CSOs). The analysis of CSO initiatives demonstrated that they also benefited from more opportunities of keeping users - especially hard to reach users - in touch with their initiatives and of creating networks that are 'resilient'. At the same time, it seems necessary to reflect on how these advantages associated with a rapid digital transition interact with the inequalities that this phenomenon helps to foster or create. For this reason, it is important to observe how the use of digital technologies by civil society has interacted with the dynamics related to the digital divide and digital inequalities, by mapping the best practices implemented to make this process as inclusive as possible. At the same time, it is important to understand how the interaction of various organisations with new technologies has influenced the organisation of their internal dynamics, responsibilities and roles.

Research questions:

- *When dealing with the digital transition, have CSOs considered strategies to involve those without digital devices, digital literacy and/or skills? If yes, how?*
- *What are the advantages and disadvantages brought by the digital transition process in the relationship between CSOs and users?*
- *What kind of new roles are needed within CSOs in order to better manage the digital transition process?*
- *What kind of hybrid (online and face-to-face) user activities have CSOs developed after lockdown periods? Are these formats still in use?*

Digitalisation at the organisational level

Digitalisation has had a profound effect on organisational structures, processes, practices, routines, spaces and work patterns across sectors influencing civil society organisations, public organisations and private organisations. Since the various lockdowns, many organisations have adopted hybrid ways of working. This has had a particularly strong effect on working conditions and job displacement. Across the three cycles, RESISTIRÉ showed how the ongoing digitalisation of employment had a mixed impact on workplaces, improving some aspects such as accessibility for people with disabilities, parents, and rural inhabitants, while also exacerbating existing inequalities and creating new ones. For example, the lack of access to appropriate digital resources was challenging in the transition to working from home, as many struggled to understand the multitude of digital tools and services that they now had to utilise on a day-to-day basis along with reconciling digital needs and care within households. This project does not have scope to explore the impact of digitalisation at the organisational level, but the following questions emerge for further research.

Research questions:

- *To what extent can digitalisation mitigate, reproduce or create new inequalities in organisations? Which digitalisation strategies work/do not work from an intersectional perspective?*
- *How can we use digitalisation as an opportunity at the organisational level to develop more inclusive organisations?*

2.4 Research Agenda on Gender+ Inclusive Green Spaces

The global environmental crisis remains an acute problem in post COVID-19 times. A broad range of issues such as urban planning, clean air and green spaces are amongst the important themes within the pan-European discussion on environmental justice (Axelsson et al., 2021). While the environmental crisis pre-dates COVID-19, it has been acknowledged that the pandemic crisis resulted in a deepening of inequalities in this domain, and thus universal and equal access to green spaces in the post-COVID-19 world requires scrutiny. The issue of access to green spaces, and more particularly, intersectional inequalities associated with this, has been highlighted in the three cycles of the RESISTIRÉ project. The findings demonstrate the gender+ character of such inequalities, yet some gaps in knowledge on this topic remain. Such gaps will be explored in this Research Agenda, with a specific focus on access to green spaces, defined in a broad sense, including public parks, community gardens, city farms, and places undergoing a process of 'wilding'. Several key themes related to this topic have been identified throughout the project research, namely **(1) benefits of inclusive access to green spaces, and of expanding access for all groups; (2) inequalities and obstacles related to accessing green spaces (3) inequalities related to decision-making and planning for the creation of, and access to, green spaces.**

Benefits of equal access to green spaces

Findings from the three cycles of the RESISTIRÉ project in relation to **the benefits of accessing green spaces**, which are a vital part of people's lives and wellbeing, are manifold. At a very basic level, it has been argued that the prevention and reduction of health risks for all groups due to environmental pollution should be on the top of the EU environmental justice policy agenda (Stovell et al., 2021). This aim, in part, is achieved by ensuring equal access to green spaces, a reduction in exposure to environmental pollutants, and allowing all citizens to make environmentally conscious consumption choices (Ganzleben & Kazmierczak, 2020). It needs to be emphasised, however, that this is based on a narrow understanding of green spaces (e.g., parks) while data collected for the RESISTIRÉ project shows that green spaces can be understood in a much broader context, with different ways of engagement with green areas and with nature.

The narratives collected during the first cycle illustrated the benefits of various types of greenspaces. An example included a female participant in Croatia reporting the benefits to her wellbeing and general quality of life of being able to access nature in various ways - such as swimming and beekeeping. This participant, who has a physical disability, was

able to leave the urban centre she lived in to access the benefits of green spaces. However, the narratives from the first cycle also illustrate that some participants were denied access to green spaces and that this had negative effects on their mental health. This was especially the case for individuals from lower socio-economic status backgrounds and for women parenting alone. Better stories of being able to access green spaces and get outside in nature in the widest sense, collected during the first cycle, included: 1) a bottom-up initiative in Belfast that developed a community urban garden in a formerly grey space; 2) 'safety walks' in the Finnish city Turku to engage its citizens in creating safer and more equal public spaces, including green spaces; 3) a Greater London Authority that awarded grants to community projects; 4) bottom-up activities in several French cities with a particular focus on women. On the other hand, the first cycle analysis of RAS identified a study conducted in Greece highlighting concerns over urban space. These concerns came to light during the pandemic as people were spending more time in their immediate areas and thus became increasingly aware of the benefits of being able to access green spaces, and of the issues regarding the condition of green spaces in their areas. The issues reported included the quality of public spaces, walking conditions and cycling facilities.

In the first cycle, it was recommended that existing public green spaces need to be improved while new ones should also be created. These spaces should be accessible, especially to the vulnerable, even during crises including lockdowns. While access should be available and free for all, some groups are more likely to be more in need of access to green spaces than others. Examples include people with disabilities, senior citizens, and young children - particularly those who do not have access to private green spaces at home. In the third cycle, evidence also emerged about the healing aspects of regular access to green spaces, as was illustrated in several of the narratives, where some respondents retrospectively referred to outdoors activities as beneficial to their mental health during the COVID-19 pandemic. Access was also highlighted in the context of overcrowding, which in Europe usually affects vulnerable groups, especially those from lower socio-economic backgrounds. For those groups, free access to green spaces can be a crucial resource.

It was also noted during the third cycle of Open Studios that green spaces can be a source of conflict within local communities. One example provided related to intergenerational conflicts already existing in communities, which can be translated into tensions about how to use a newly created green space in a neighbourhood, or whose usage is to be prioritised. For that reason, it was noted that careful design and inclusive consultation processes with diverse stakeholders need to be adopted when designing new green spaces or reviewing existing ones. However, it was emphasised that green spaces can also provide a space for conflict resolution and reconciliation. This can take place, for example, when different groups are mobilised to work together on the revitalisation of existing spaces or setting up new green areas.

In relation to the theme which relates to benefits of access, unequal **availability of accessible space** has been highlighted as a knowledge gap. The needs of different age

groups involved in the space, such as older people, teenagers, and small children, should be considered. The use of green spaces for other purposes, such as public meetings or education, are also among the topics which require more exploration. While the benefits of such versatile uses have been highlighted in the course of the research, further scrutiny is required to fully establish the ways in which this could be achieved.

The benefits brought by initiatives led by CSOs and community groups, especially in relation to reclaiming neglected green spaces or re-wilding grey spaces also stands out as a significant gap in research that needs further exploration. This is particularly important considering that, during the third cycle of the project, there was no CSO or community initiatives directly related to green spaces identified by the National Researchers. Finally, the role of municipalities, for example in relation to the ways in which unused land is approached, how they support bottom-up community initiatives.

Research questions:

- *How can we channel existing community impulses to create new, universally accessible and gender+ inclusive green commons?*
- *How can we make green commons adaptable depending on the time of day, the needs of users, and different groups (e.g., young children, older people)?*
- *In what ways can communities be mobilised to ensure that different vulnerable groups work together to create or revitalise green spaces that are inclusive and beneficial from a gender+ perspective?*
- *How can green spaces be used for various purposes benefiting different users and social groups, for e.g., public meetings, sports, education, cultural events, and other recreational activities, particularly in relation to vulnerable groups?*

Intersecting inequalities in relation to accessing green spaces

Despite the proven benefits that green spaces have for both individuals and the community, the research conducted by the RESISTIRÉ project, as well as international studies, suggest that **there are important inequalities in relation to accessing green spaces**. Crucially, socio-economic status and social class stood out. It became evident through data analysis that, to a certain extent, inequalities related to people's access to green spaces increased during the pandemic as lower socio-economic groups relied on public rather than private green spaces. This was particularly important from the point of view of gentrification. As part of this process, urban areas that have undergone 'greening' become highly sought after on the housing market, thereby pushing out people on lower incomes and those from vulnerable groups. The consequent displacement of those from lower socio-economic backgrounds effectively prevents them from benefitting from any positive urban (re)development, like the expansion of green spaces (Kerremans & Lionello, 2021). **Our findings also suggest that access to green spaces can be also affected by intersecting inequalities**. For example, age, in conjunction with socio-economic background, was an important factor in relation to unequal access, particularly during the pandemic. While restricted access to green

spaces for older people during the pandemic was specific to the public health measures, overall limitations related to age-inclusive green spaces became apparent. In particular, there is evidence of younger cohorts dominating such spaces, for example public parks, therefore not 'allowing' the older groups to fully enjoy them, or, in some cases, preventing them from feeling safe in such places. The divide between young and old people was discussed in this context, as was disability. For example, the availability of infrastructure meeting the needs of various age groups was recognised as sometimes problematic. Similarly, the issue of accessibility to green spaces by people with different abilities was also identified as an issue. Furthermore, the issue of safety was discussed in the context of green spaces that remain empty and secluded and thus can pose safety threats for women and other vulnerable groups. While safety remains an issue in relation to accessing green spaces, some better stories have been identified throughout the RESISTIRÉ study. For example, one of the pilot projects funded by RESISTIRÉ, Aqi, worked on making a park in Barcelona accessible and safe for women, people with disabilities and those from migrant backgrounds to use regularly. Aqi also successfully worked towards reducing tensions amongst the various groups using the park.

The lack of available data on intersecting inequalities related to accessing green spaces represents one of the main research gaps in this theme. More relevant data would be of benefit as the overall topic remains under-researched, particularly in the context of large surveys. Accessible, representative and disaggregated data (e.g., by factors such as socioeconomic status, gender and/or age) is required to adequately study the intersections of various inequalities in relation to accessing green spaces (Stovell et al., 2021). How unequal access to green spaces affects different vulnerable groups also requires more qualitative scrutiny. In particular, the question of increasing inequalities in relation to accessing green spaces post-pandemic remain an under-explored issue deserving further study. Collecting data/information on more versatile initiatives promoting inclusive access to green spaces could also provide an important avenue for further research.

Furthermore, the question of access and increasing access for all may also be explored in the context of the ongoing **gentrification of urban areas**, as well as the cost-of-living crisis, which may affect where people live, or whether they can easily afford public transport which allows them to access green spaces.

As gentrification in the context of the cost-of-living crisis is likely to result in the further displacement of people from lower socio-economic backgrounds, **more scrutiny should be also given to the links between close access to green spaces, and social and economic resources.** As identified through the RESISTIRÉ research, social class constitutes an important inequality ground (Axelsson et al., 2021) and can be interpreted in terms of 'deficient resilience' (Forbes et al., 2009). This needs to be considered and understood from a gender+ and a feminist institutionalism perspective. Through such theoretical perspectives, *attention is given to how issues related to environmental justice are located at macro and meso levels rather than at groups and individuals made vulnerable* (cf. Deveaux, 2006). This knowledge gap should be explored further.

Finally, the **complexity of vulnerability** is one of the possible topics to explore in future research in relation to green spaces. This will help to provide a better understanding of the needs of vulnerable groups as well as the possibility of recognising vulnerabilities beyond the 'traditional' categories.

Research questions:

- *What kind of data can be collected to ensure that adequate knowledge is generated in relation to accessing green spaces from an intersectional perspective?*
- *How can we ensure that green spaces are available to everyone and how do we reduce the grey-green divides between different groups?*
- *How do we design public green spaces so that diverse groups of people, including those from vulnerable groups, are comfortable in them and are encouraged to seek them out?*
- *How do we ensure that public green spaces are safe for everyone and how do we prevent (gender-based) violence at times when green spaces are sparsely populated?*
- *How can we ensure that 'vulnerability' is approached from an intersectional perspective in order to gain a better understanding regarding unequal access?*

Inequalities in decision-making and planning for the creation of, and access to green spaces

Unequal participation in decision-making and planning for green spaces was also an important theme emerging from the RESISTIRÉ research, as members of vulnerable groups have been inadequately included in urban planning processes, including those around creating accessible green spaces. Another issue emerging from our research relates to the unequal management of green spaces, as well as frequent 'discriminatory policing' which has a negative effect on the uptake of green spaces by certain marginalised groups. On a more general level, research results also highlighted that women remain largely absent from environmental policy formulation and from decision-making, while, at the same time, being largely affected by environmental changes and by environmental policymaking. In terms of ways forward, the civic response to the crisis was discussed at length and provided useful insights to the question of participatory decision-making processes. For example, participants who took part in the workshop focused on tackling isolation and exclusion emphasised that it is **necessary to find ways of transforming the window of opportunity provided by the pandemic into a permanent change**. The analysis highlights the importance of minimising bureaucratic obstacles and encouraging openness to change. Furthermore, communication, collaboration and innovation were highlighted as integral to moving forward post crisis in an inclusive and impactful manner. Innovation was mentioned in relation to encouraging participation and in relation to funding. Amongst the main points arising from this workshop was the need for strategies to be built into organisational design to

increase involvement with 'hard to reach' groups. Also, noteworthy in relation to green spaces accessibility is that within vulnerable communities there are hierarchies, and that CSOs and policymakers need to be cognisant of this to be able to negotiate such challenges. Indeed, understanding the 'complexity of vulnerability' in relation to accessing green spaces is key to reducing the barriers encountered by marginalised individuals and groups.

The lack of involvement of vulnerable groups to 'solve' problems can be linked with the need for decision-making to be more inclusive and involve participatory methods. A main finding from RESISTIRÉ is that there was a lack of women's representation in state responses to the pandemic as the relevant decision-making positions were mainly held by men. Most of the pandemic-related measures identified in European countries were at the national government level (with some exceptions observed in countries with a federal system), sometimes with the support of expert committees created ad-hoc to deal with the emergency (Kerremans & Lionello, 2022). This resulted in an absence of a gender+ sensitivity in policy responses and in measures aimed at solving problems at the social level more widely. Research has shown that decisions made about and during lockdowns generally impacted those experiencing inequalities more than those in secure positions. These decisions were made in a top-down fashion without involvement from vulnerable individuals/groups. As this issue is also applicable to the subject of gender+ inclusive green spaces, increased research scrutiny should be given to the way in which decision-making is conducted. Moreover, including local communities in decisions about green space activities so that green spaces become more attractive to them can go towards genuine community and solidarity building. This should be further explored.

Participatory planning processes should thus be further investigated in order to establish ways forward towards more inclusive environmental decision-making.

Collecting 'better stories' and good practices from different European cities, and making them more visible to the public, could provide an avenue for such investigation. How the communities are engaged in consultation processes regarding green spaces, should also be investigated. This issue is also important in the context of gentrification, as questions emerge around the actors involved in the initiatives, as well as around the target groups, and the effects that gentrification has on local communities. The interactions between activists, policymakers, and advocacy groups in different national and local contexts may also be further explored. In this context, more scrutiny will be required to identify the ways in which coalitions between CSOs, community groups and public organisations have emerged to date, and in what way these can be formed in the future. The issue related to the political context and the ownership of land would also require further scrutiny. As has been discussed in the third cycle Open Studio, different national and local contexts are important as the private/public division can be understood differently depending on the legislation. For that reason, the universal right to use the space can be sometimes problematic. The question of what entitlements the general public may have in relation to the different types of land within urban spaces remains an important knowledge gap within the last theme.

Research questions:

- *What can policymakers do to make access to green spaces more inclusive?*
- *How do we prevent discriminatory policing by public authorities and local law enforcement?*
- *How can we facilitate more equal and diverse local management of public green spaces?*
- *How can a fully participatory consultation process and decision-making process regarding green spaces be achieved at different levels?*
- *What are the consequences of different land ownership laws and policies on the creation of new green spaces and equal access to existing areas?*
- *What role do CSOs have in working with individuals/policymakers to ensure equal access to and use of green spaces?*

2.5 Research Agenda on Civic Responses to Crisis

Civil society organisations played a key role in providing an immediate response to the pandemic (Tageo et al., 2021), engaging in activities aimed at repairing the damages to health, society, and the economy that were caused or exacerbated by the pandemic and pandemic-related policies. Including the perspective of civil society organisations and learning from their experiences has been a key objective throughout the RESISTIRÉ project but it was given particular attention in the third cycle through the mapping of 128 civil society initiatives representing promising practices of support provision to meet the needs of vulnerable people during the pandemic (Cibin et al., 2023). 'Creative Civic Responses to Crises' was also the theme of an Open Studio in the third cycle. These activities offered insights into practices and kinds of action that can contribute to reversing the developments that deepen inequality. They also highlighted the need for further research to better understand the role civil society organisations can play in a crisis.

The Research and Activism Nexus

Civil society organisations (CSOs) have always played a key role in research with vulnerable groups, helping academic researchers reach the most vulnerable communities and orienting them towards the field. In recent years, many CSOs have engaged in action-research of their own, supporting their activism in the field with research findings and activities (Cibin et al., 2023; Kerremans & Denis, 2023). RESISTIRÉ research has highlighted the significance of such research for the identification of problems and development of solutions that address gender+ inequalities and possibilities of more inclusive action and policy (Cibin et al., 2023). Research by and with CSOs proves to be particularly significant in crisis situations where prior relationships of trust play a key role in accessing vulnerable communities that remain outside the reach of public services and whose needs remain unidentified and unaddressed.

Research questions:

- *What strategies can be developed to expand the field of action-research through collaboration between academic institutions and CSOs?*
- *How can action-research by and with CSOs help ensure that civic responses are inclusive and reduce gender+ inequalities?*
- *How has the collaboration between CSOs and academic researchers contributed to identifying the needs of vulnerable populations as well as assessing the impact of specific initiatives?*
- *What are the challenges faced in such collaboration and how can these challenges be addressed by academic institutions and funders?*
- *CSOs may have the openness, but not the time and the resources to research the 'root causes' or underlying factors of the issues they address in their activism. What are some of the better stories of action-research bringing together academics and activists in mutually generative ways?*
- *What are the better stories of researchers becoming activists - especially in terms of facilitating creative, effective, inclusive crisis response?*

Bridging experience and creativity: organisational flexibility and innovative practices

COVID-19 highlighted the significant role of civil society in responding to -crises. RESISTIRÉ's third cycle research found specific features and actions that enabled CSOs to navigate the pandemic challenges, to craft creative responses to overlapping crises, and to offer effective support to vulnerable people (Cibin et al., 2023). Civil society proved to be more agile and act faster than the public sector and were able to offer rapid answers to the issues that emerged during the pandemic. This was because CSOs were able to take advantage of their organisational flexibility, creativity, and, in some circumstances, even their ingenuity, enabling them to experiment with novel approaches that ultimately produced positive results (Cibin et al., 2023). Institutional frameworks played a strong role in these dynamics. Less bureaucracy and resistance to change in the context of the pandemic crisis enabled many CSOs to test innovative solutions.

The pandemic crisis and its multi-layered challenges stimulated creative civic response. In better stories of civic response to crisis as identified by RESISTIRÉ, CSOs have learned to improvise. This capacity was built on prior experiences—along with those of other organisations—in crisis circumstances and in developing organisational flexibility to react swiftly to sudden changes. This involves being able to both follow an experience-based plan for how to react in such circumstances and develop improvisational skills that allow them to adjust to the situation (Cibin et al., 2023). These skills were often the outcome of enhanced reflexivity, which raised awareness of competences within the organisations and, as a result, opened the door to the possibility of allowing more autonomy to employees, volunteers, and users. (Cibin et al., 2023).

Research questions:

- *In CSOs' attempts to provide immediate response to crisis situations, what role does path dependence play and what are the dynamics through which innovative solutions are stimulated?*
- *What tools can be developed within organisations to train reflexivity and enable awareness of one's own response possibilities when a crisis arises?*
- *What is the role of mutual learning in civic response? What enables greater and deeper learning for all parties involved?*
- *How can for-profit organisations learn from non-profit organisations about being inclusive and intersectional?*
- *What are the differences between various types of organisations (formal vs informal, small vs big, etc.) in their capacities to offer rapid solutions during crisis situations?*
- *What are the better stories of innovative solutions developed during the pandemic by CSOs to mitigate inequalities? What allowed/hindered their institutionalisation? What happened to those solutions and the organisations themselves in the transition to a post-pandemic world?*

Multi-actor, collective, and participatory ways of organising and decision-making

The response of feminist and LGBTQI+ organisations to overlapping crises offer several key insights to learn from:

- multi-actor, collective, and participatory ways of organising and decision-making;
- using an intersectional lens to expand their reach and to refine their services to address differential needs;
- making invisible forms of gendered inequality and discrimination visible;
- investing in community-building both prior to, during and after the crisis;
- creating intersectional alliances and communities around the horizontal framework of rights-based 'solidarity' based on mutual learning and transformation, rather than top-down, hierarchical frameworks of 'help' or 'charity';
- monitoring the effects of the crisis in its aftermath.

In the Turkish context, close collaboration between CSOs (particularly feminist organisations) and the municipalities proved to be key to equality work and to reaching the most vulnerable (e.g. Pandemic Map of Turkish Municipalities, Deep Poverty Network, etc.). Expert consulted as part of RESISTIRÉ research highlighted that the women's movement had been much better organised compared to public authorities and municipalities and during pandemic, online networking among women's organisations had made them even more efficient in terms of providing support to women across the country. An expert representing a European-level organisation also mentioned the significance of collaboration and networking between different CSOs as

a better story of responding to the pandemic (Sandström et al., 2022).

Feminist and LGBTQI+ organisations were key particularly in the struggle against gender-based violence, yet they were often not financially supported by the governments and were typically excluded from crisis resilience funding (Altınay et al., 2022). Furthermore, anti-gender policies and discourse in certain countries have limited the work and impact of feminist and LGBTQI+ organisations by demonising and stifling them.

Research questions:

- *What (public and private) mechanisms would ensure feminist and LGBTQI+ organisations to have access to sustainable funding, particularly during crises and in countries where anti-gender policies are dominant?*
- *How can the experience of collaboration and networking by feminist and LGBTQI+ organisations during the pandemic be shared, disseminated, and finally integrated into the work of other civic initiatives?*
- *What has been the impact of the presence or absence of such networks among feminist and LGBTQI+ organisations in different parts of Europe - particularly in terms of developing inclusive solutions to pandemic inequalities?*
- *How have anti-gender policies impacted the presence or absence of such networks and collaborations - and vice versa?*
- *What role have collective and participatory ways of organising and decision-making played in different contexts across Europe - in the context of the pandemic and other crisis situations?*
- *What are some examples of multi-actor, collective, and participatory ways of organising and decision-making?*
- *What are the ways of making invisible forms of gendered inequality and discrimination visible?*
- *In what ways can investing in community-building both prior to, during, and after a crisis be beneficial?*
- *To what extent do pre-existing communities (of action and solidarity) impact crisis response efforts? How do crises themselves and the contextual factors surrounding them affect community building and organising? By exploring the interplay between pre-existing community building, crisis dynamics, and contextual factors, what can be learned about the factors that contribute to effective response in times of crisis?*
- *How do intersectional alliances and communities based on mutual learning and transformation promote rights-based 'solidarity'?*
- *What are the impacts of monitoring on a crisis response? How can monitoring processes be improved to measure the efficacy of public response as well as of civil society response?*
- *How can people with different skills be incorporated into crisis response? What impact does such inclusion have on the efficacy of crisis response from a gender+ intersectional perspective?*

Building alliances: (Local and national) public services and CSOs

Better stories of civic response to crises identified by RESISTIRÉ highlighted complementary state-civil society relations (Dayson and Damm, 2020), most notably when CSOs were involved in decision-making, coordination, and activities related to public services (Cibin et al., 2023). In the cases analysed, various public institutions demonstrated the feasibility and effectiveness of collaborating on and testing innovative solutions based on the experience of those working directly with vulnerable people. In situations of uncertainty, various public authorities began to recognise the vital intermediary role played by CSOs and they showed a greater predisposition to collaborate with them. However, there were also various cases where these collaborations were not possible or where the public authorities hindered the work of CSOs. There were instances where initiatives were supported by local institutions but were stalled at the national level (Cibin et al., 2023). Moreover, governments frequently fell short of creating adequate channels for coordination and communication between relevant ministries and civil society actors during the pandemic crisis. As a result, they could not utilise the experiences and skills of CSOs in reaching out to vulnerable groups and developing effective responses to inequalities (Altınay et al., 2022). This was particularly the case in countries where increasingly illiberal forms of governance lead to anti-civil society and anti-gender politics (Kuhar & Paternotte, 2017; Petö, 2021).

The experts consulted as part of RESISTIRÉ stressed the significance of expanding the opportunities for collaboration both between public services and CSOs and between CSOs, finding methods and tools that could enable the design of experience-based policies through the sharing of information and better stories as well as continuous dialogue with stakeholders (Cibin et al., 2023).

Research questions:

- *What tools can be designed to facilitate a continuous dialogue between public services and CSOs with the goal of co-designing and co-implementing crisis response plans?*
- *What tools can be developed to encourage the creation of relationships between CSOs and public institutions before crises take place? In situations where these relationships were in place before the pandemic, what difference did they make in the provision of public services to vulnerable communities?*
- *What kind of collaborations between CSOs and public institutions can be formed to allow more innovative approaches to support vulnerable people? What are some better stories of such collaborations?*
- *What factors contribute to the success or failure of collaborations between public authorities and CSOs and among CSOs? What are the characteristics of more effective collaboration, and how can these be fostered or developed? How did the pandemic crisis influence the relations between state and civil society in different parts of Europe and with what consequences for gender+ inequalities?*

Enabling environment for CSOs in the face of crisis

In the areas of research conducted as part of RESISTIRÉ, creating a better story is not just the result of civil society's capacity to start a new initiative or maintain existing ones. Certain structural conditions at the institutional level proved to be significant. Most of the initiatives would not have become better stories without funding from national, regional, or local public authorities, often made available to respond specifically to the pandemic (Cibin et al., 2023).

The pandemic demonstrated how it is possible and essential to boost funding from public authorities to CSOs. CSOs need to count on stable forms of funding from the public authorities to become sustainable and develop resilience. The pandemic showed how civil society initiatives, if better funded and supported, can help to mitigate inequalities among vulnerable groups. This response to an emergency situation must be transformed into a more stable condition for CSOs (Cibin et al., 2023).

Even though CSOs enhanced the problem-solving capacity of contemporary societies, these potentials have to be balanced against the weaknesses of CSOs, which also calls for policy responses that strike a balance between controlling and enabling measures in terms of regulation and support.

In general, it is vital to find ways of transforming what was a window of opportunity during the pandemic into a permanent situation. It is important to create room for the experience and creativity of civil society by minimising bureaucratic obstacles and fostering an openness to change. To this end, creating coalitions formed by CSOs and public organisations has become crucial for the effective management of complex issues affecting the most vulnerable particularly during poli-crises (Cibin et al., 2023).

Research questions:

- *Which public financing systems can be considered effective in enabling CSOs to be economically sustainable in the long term?*
- *What would a political eco-system that stimulates innovative solutions look like? What is the role of different forms of governmentality in creating the environment CSOs operate in?*
- *How can public authorities stimulate the emergence of civic responses during crisis situations and create an enabling environment for CSOs to operate?*
- *How can the advantages CSOs offer to society, and indeed to governments, be strengthened while minimising any disadvantages?*
- *What is the right policy framework for governments and CSOs to balance their respective interests while realising the potential of civil society to reduce inequalities in public service?*
- *When CSOs are given long-term, flexible funding (as opposed to short-term project-based funding), how does this impact their capacity to respond to crises?*

- *What are the economic gains that have resulted from (preventive) CSO response to mitigating the effects of the pandemic for the most vulnerable communities and individuals - in addition to their humanitarian and political impact?*
- *In terms of regenerative activism, what elements constitute an enabling environment that adequately meets the needs of activists and CSOs professionals? How can systems and structures be designed to support the physical, emotional, and mental well-being of activists, while also fostering a culture of creativity and solidarity?*
- *In authoritarian political systems where anti-gender policies prevail, what tactics have civil society organisations (CSOs) employed to effectively respond to crises, and what factors contribute to the success of these tactics?*

2.6 Research Agenda on Gender-based Violence

The research conducted within the RESISTIRÉ project in the third cycle of activities has shed light on the paramount role played by civil society organisations and initiatives to provide quick and safe responses to the needs of survivors of gender-based violence. Civil society organisations have adopted innovative ways of reaching out to survivors in the crisis context, while ensuring anonymity and safety. Many of the initiatives mapped by the project also showed the sensitivity of these organisations to intersecting inequalities when addressing gender-based violence, as opposed to standardised and insufficient responses usually set up by national authorities. Linking to the second cycles research agendas (Kerremans & Denis, 2023), this research agenda stresses the need to conduct further research into the better stories of civic responses to gender-based violence. The impact of the pandemic crisis on gender-based violence also drew attention to the importance of prevention programmes and their impact in transforming gender roles, and to closely monitor the impact of political backlash against gender equality. Adopting intersectionality as one of the paradigms of analysis, RESISTIRÉ reiterates the importance to improve knowledge on the complexity of gender-based violence, in terms of forms and the diversity of groups affected. In this sense, the pandemic crisis contributed to bringing attention to the violence that is perpetrated in specific work contexts, where it is still largely invisible.

CSOs played an important role in supporting survivors of gender-based violence: how to learn from their actions to improve public responses?

The third cycle of RESISTIRÉ's research has focused on the identification and analysis of the so-called "better stories". This focus has enabled an understanding of what capacities, competences, and capitals (social, symbolic, etc.) were acquired or strengthened during the COVID-19 pandemic and could be valorised during subsequent emergencies and socioeconomic crises. Various initiatives mapped in the three cycles include crowdfunding, expansion of services on-line and by phone,

increasing availability of shelters, and innovative ways of reaching out to survivors while ensuring anonymity and safety.

Four better stories of civic responses to gender-based violence stand out: civil society's capacity for **innovative and rapid responses** to crisis situations; cross-sectoral **collaboration between public and private actors**, and a **broadening and change** in the **conceptualisation and understanding of gender-based violence**. Lastly, civil society organisations' (CSOs) approaches and activities also reflect **sensitivity to the diversity of experiences and needs of survivors of gender-based violence** (women with children, older women, LGBTIQ+ persons, etc.), incorporating some degree of intersectionality into their actions, when policies usually lag behind.

Among the lessons learned from the pandemic, the analysis of CSO initiatives points to the need to strengthen their collaboration with public authorities and with other civil society organisations in order to develop better policies and provide a better coordinated response to multi-dimensional needs. Coordination between relevant services is also at the heart of EP's proposal for a new directive on combating violence against women and domestic violence. However, a study commissioned by FEMM (2022) points out existing **gaps in safety measures such as procedures for risk assessment, coordination between the police and other services, and training** for law enforcement and other public officials dealing with gender-based violence.

It is also apparent how overburdened and saturated services were during the crisis. **Service-providers** in the field of gender-based violence (and other) have been exposed to increased workload, with high level of stress, limited funding, health-related constraints, among others. Especially, secondary trauma was identified as an acute risk across caring professions, policy, advocacy, and other practitioners who work with survivors of gender-based violence. Across RESISTIRÉ's research, it was emphasised the importance to support service providers, address the impact of multiple crises on their health and on the resilience of support services. These are also issues that need further research. The Pilot Project "Exhale: Moving through secondary trauma together", led by the NGO Chayn, explores the effects of secondary trauma on the mind, body, emotions, and behaviours, and how to recognise these effects in ourselves and others.

Research questions:

- *What are the lessons learned from the pandemic regarding gender-based violence, in terms of the solutions /opportunities developed to overcome obstacles and inequalities by individuals, CSOs and policymakers?*
- *Is coordination between policymakers and CSOs delivering better results in addressing gender-based violence, if so, what models of coordination prove more effective? How can coordination be framed so that it acknowledges the CSOs' contributions, without simultaneously freeing the state and local authorities from the responsibility to address gender-based violence?*
- *How can national actors and Member States incorporate lessons learned from the*

response provided by CSOs?

- *Does the need to strengthen victims' access to justice and to reinforce their protection offer new scenarios for the collaboration of public and private actors?*
- *What is the impact of the pandemic and the polycrisis context on the service providers? How can resilience be fostered within this group?*
- *Do private actors, led by CSOs, have operational advantages in responding nimbly to crisis situations? If so, what are these advantages of the conditions that enable them, and how these advantages could be capitalised in the response to gender-based violence?*
- *What are the enablers of public-private partnerships and what are the main difficulties?*
- *How can improving the wellbeing of front-line workers also have a positive impact on the services provided to survivors?*

More research is needed to measure the impact and effectiveness of prevention programmes

Prevention is a key obligation in the harmonised response to gender-based violence put forward by the Istanbul Convention (Council of Europe, 2011), but crisis-related initiatives and policies have not often included it in their agenda. Examples of existing prevention programmes and actions have been collected by the Council of Europe (2014), pointing out the lack of robust evaluation.

Through RESISTIRÉ, two pilot projects address prevention of gender-based violence through sports and non-formal education in two different contexts (Serbia and Greece). Results of both projects will provide important information about the potential of sports to teach equality, respect and inclusion to future generations.

At the same time, there is urgent need for **evidence on the impact and effectiveness** of existing prevention programmes in changing prevailing attitudes about the roles of men and women in society, and attitude towards gender identities and sexual orientations that differ from the dominant norm. It is important to know which programmes are succeeding, how, what actors are included, factors/conditions/methodologies are proving effective and allow for the programmes to be replicated across Europe. Another important aspect to consider is the organisational culture and structure of those actors implementing such programmes, and the impact that these elements might have on the implementation and success of the programmes, but also what organisational changes are produced at the organisational level. In case of sports and sporting clubs, what is the impact of their organisational structure and culture in perpetuating violence, how this can be changed?

Impact and effectiveness should also be measured with regard to different geographical and political contexts. Ample and varied evidence on the impact of prevention programmes is needed to support better policymaking and better use of public funding.

Research questions:

- *Which of the prevention programmes have proved effective in changing societal attitudes and norms?*
- *What are the actors/factors/methodologies implemented in these programmes that appear as promising to foster this change?*
- *Is non-formal education among the youth effective in producing long-term changes in gender roles?*
- *What is the role of organisations and agencies like sporting clubs (but also other institutions involved with the youth) in promoting changes in gender roles or reinforcing patriarchal/homophobic and transphobic attitudes? To what extent their organisational structure, culture, rules are fostering unequal relations that potentially result in violence?*
- *What is the impact of prevention programmes on organisational structures and culture of workplaces/sporting clubs/etc.?*

COVID-19 and the anti-gender movement in Europe: what is the impact of the current political situation on the response to gender-based violence in the future?

The emergency status declared all over Europe to face the exceptional circumstances of the COVID-19 crisis in 2020 has urged national governments to adopt urgent measures to support shelters and organisations helping survivors of gender-based violence. **In public discourse and media, attention to the impact of gender-based violence** during the lockdown seem to have increased, following also the launch of awareness raising campaigns in different countries (Cibin et al., 2021; Sandström et al., 2022).

If indeed awareness and political attention has increased, the nature and effects of such increased attention to the phenomenon of gender-based violence and the consequences of lockdowns and the economic crisis is yet to be understood. Still few EU Member States explicitly recognised gender-based violence against women as a form of discrimination or equality issue as required by the Istanbul Convention (De Vido & Sosa, 2021).

During the pandemic, governments and private actors have released funding to support shelters and generally organisations providing services for survivors of gender-based violence. Whether these changes in awareness and public/private intervention to support services will persist, what impact it will bring on the response to gender-based violence in the polycrisis context is also a matter for future research.

Research on the **quality of democracy in Europe** is a priority concern (see the list of [projects funded through Horizon Europe on democracy](#)), and the quality of democracy has an impact on policymaking and gender equality. Future research should focus on democracy and its relationship with gender equality from an intersectional perspective.

In the background of this concern, the rising anti-gender and anti-feminist movement across Europe that links to the far-right action against sexual rights and against racial and ethnic minorities. The COVID-19 crisis has also appeared in a context of the emergence of populist and far-right governments across Europe and beyond. This new political setting has also opened the **space for backlashes** in the degree of protection of women's rights and freedoms in areas like reproductive rights and the rights of LGBTIQ+. An example is the Hungarian ban on abortion that was passed during the pandemic, and the Turkish withdrawal from the Istanbul Convention (March, 2021). Many narratives and expert opinions collected by RESISTIRÉ have stressed that this political backlash is having negative effects on people safety and respect for their rights and freedom (Sandström et al., 2022).

At the same time, at national and global level, feminist movements like the MeToo have been mobilising to expose systematic violations of human rights. In connection to this, the MeToo movement has contributed to shed light on patriarchal practices and systematic violence in sectors like sports and entertainment, but also the domestic care sector. In Greece, for example, the feminist movement has led to increased awareness of gender equality issues among coaches and actors of the sports sector. Future research would need to delve into the impact of this complex political landscape on policymaking, on social cohesion and democracy, on forms of social mobilisation, as well as on the resilience of human rights protection mechanisms.

Research Questions:

- *To what extent does the quality of democracy in different countries affect the spread of anti-gender discourses?*
- *How did anti-gender discourses play out during the pandemic and in the current polycrisis context in different countries?*
- *How do anti-gender movements affect policies/policymaking/representation and services to support victims of gender-based violence against women and LGBTIQ+ communities?*
- *Has there been an increase in awareness and visibility of gender-based violence among society and policymakers? If so, what impact is it having on policy response and on social mobilisation? What forms of violence have been made more visible? Was there an improvement in the social and political understanding of the intersectional dimensions of gender-based violence?*
- *What is the impact of the anti-gender movement on the functioning of national and supranational monitoring mechanisms?*
- *What is the impact of feminist movements and campaigns across Europe on societal changes about the perception of gender-based violence? What is their impact regarding the anti-gender backlash?*

Research on gender-based violence should include all different forms of violence and adopt an intersectional lens

The proposal for a EU Directive (EC, 2022) on combating violence against women and domestic violence adopts a **broad conceptualisation** of gender-based violence that encompasses sexual violence, including rape, female genital mutilation, forced marriage, forced abortion or sterilisation, trafficking in human beings for sexual exploitation, stalking, sexual harassment, femicide, hate speech and gender-based crimes and various forms of online violence ("cyber-violence"), such as non-consensual dissemination or manipulation of intimate material, cyberstalking and cyber-bullying.

While results in the third cycle have pointed at the impact of the pandemic on sexual and reproductive rights, future research should be careful to collect data on different forms and dimensions of violence and the impact of crises on each of them. Data on forms such as female genital mutilation and forced marriage are missing, as well as data on scale and prevalence of gender-based violence perpetrated online. There is also limited quantitative data on the social and economic impacts of gender-based cyber violence on victims and other stakeholders (EPRS, 2021). EU-wide research on the legal approaches to the issue is still limited (De Vido & Sosa, 2021).

Research on scale and prevalence of each form of gender-based violence should also adopt an intersectional analysis and measure the impact on specific subgroups, such as women from minority groups, older women, and women with disabilities; and the prevalence of gender-based violence against LGBTIQ+ people. The proposed directive emphasises the need to strengthen victims' access to justice and victims' rights to adequate protection by responding directly to the specific needs of victims of violence against women and domestic violence.

Research should explore also the impact of the pandemic and other crises on gender-based violence in specific work sectors. Some data has been collected on gender-based violence in the garment industry (ILO, 2021b), but further research is needed also in other sectors like health services and the domestic and care sector, a sector that, due to its characteristics (private setting, majority of vulnerable women involved, who are usually undocumented, etc.), pose specific challenges for prevention, protection and prosecution.

Research questions:

- *What is the impact of COVID on female genital mutilation and forced marriages? To what extent does the fragmentation of EU regulation hinder the adoption of uniform and coherent measures to combat violence against women?*
- *What is the scale and prevalence of gender-based violence perpetrated online?*
- *What is the impact of gender-based violence in different sectors, e.g. domestic care sector, and health sector, in terms of prevalence and forms? What was the impact of the pandemic on violence perpetrated against these workers and its forms? Has it increased?*

3. Conclusions

This report provides an overview of the operational recommendations and research agendas that have been developed as part of the third cycle of WP6 activities. Concretely, the output consists of eight operational recommendations and six thematic research agendas.

Several of the third-cycle operational recommendations highlight the importance of health and care services during crises – especially during health crises like COVID-19 – and recognise the need for more inclusivity (i.e., better access to health services for vulnerable groups), improving not just physical but also mental health support, and ensuring more qualitative and sustainable long-term care arrangements that can weather crises. Digital services of all kinds (including health services) are also emphasised in light of the accelerated digital transitions that our societies are going through. It is imperative that this wide-ranging transformation is inclusive and equitable, and that digital inequalities are swiftly identified and countered by policy.

The increase in poverty and social exclusion that was facilitated by the pandemic needs to be addressed as well, with an eye on more inclusive and accessible social protection schemes, as well as the development of plans that can intervene to protect vulnerable groups from the various impacts of a crisis. In this regard, the recommendations of the final cycle continue to emphasise crisis preparedness and response from a feminist perspective, taking into account gender+ intersectional inequalities and utilising a holistic approach that regards crisis as a continuum. An innovative approach to funding schemes for civic responses to crises from CSOs was proposed as well. Lastly, to enable more thorough research and intersectional analysis on the impacts of (future) crises, better systematic data collection on the European level that covers various inequalities is urgently needed.

Finally, with regard to the research agendas, the final cycle has built further on some research agendas that were already covered to various degrees in prior cycles, but that still had potential for expansion (i.e., the research agendas on health inequalities and gender-based violence). Moreover, it covered some domains that were not taken up previously, like digitalisation, age and ageing, green spaces, and civic responses to crises. The newly identified knowledge gaps and research questions of these agendas will be promoted towards funders in order to ensure that innovative research is carried out across Europe beyond the duration of the RESISTIRÉ project.

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